

D7.9

Report on Dissemination Activities

PoDIUM

PDI connectivity and cooperation enablers building trust and sustainability for CCAM

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
C-ITS	Cooperative Intelligent Transport System
CCAM	Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility
CINEA	European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
CORDIS	Community Research and Development Information Service
C-V2X	Cellular Vehicle-to-Everything
D	Deliverable
DG	Directorate-General
DQN	Deep Q-Network
EU	European Union
EC	European Commission
EUCAD	European Conference on Connected and Automated Driving
GA	Grant Agreement
HMI	Human–Machine Interface
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
ITS	Intelligent Transport Systems
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LDM	Local Dynamic Map
LL	Living Lab

LTE	Long Term Evolution
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
MFI	Multisensor Fusion and Integration
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
PDI	Physical and Digital Infrastructure
RTO	Research and Technology Organisation
RSU	Roadside Units
RTR	Road Transport Research
SIS	Special Interest Session
UC	Use Case
VRU	Vulnerable Road User
V2I	Vehicle-to-Infrastructure
V2X	Vehicle-to-Everything
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This report presents the dissemination activities carried out within the PoDIUM project from October 2022 to December 2025. Building on the strategy defined in Deliverable 7.4, the consortium implemented a coordinated approach to ensure that the project's main messages, objectives, progress, and results reached relevant expert communities, industry stakeholders, policymakers, and the broader Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility (CCAM) ecosystem.

The report outlines the full range of dissemination actions: participation in conferences and events, scientific publications, exhibition activities, organisation of demonstration events and webinars, and the production of videos and dissemination materials. It summarises the core messages, target audiences, outreach approaches, and the tools and channels used, and assesses the effectiveness of the performed dissemination activities against the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) established in D7.4.

Across the project duration, PoDIUM has exceeded many of its targets. The consortium engaged in 42 conferences and external events, delivered 49 presentations, published 22 scientific papers, organised 5 webinars, participated in 11 exhibitions, produced 9 videos, and held 3 public events showcasing real-world demonstrations. These activities contributed significantly to raising awareness of PoDIUM's work, building visibility in the CCAM community, and supporting the uptake of the project's results.

1. Introduction

The [PoDIUM project](#) aims to advance key technologies in both the physical and digital infrastructure to address challenges related to road automation, telecommunications, connectivity, cooperation, data management, interoperability, and reliability. These advancements are essential for enabling the development and deployment of CCAM solutions. The dissemination activities of the project played an important role in raising awareness and ensuring that PoDIUM's work and outcomes were shared to expert communities and stakeholders in Europe and beyond.

Early in the project, the dissemination task leader prepared a comprehensive dissemination strategy and plan that would serve as the basis for all dissemination activities throughout the project lifecycle. This strategy and plan was outlined in [Deliverable 7.4](#) that was completed in March 2023 (M06). The Deliverable set the standard for the dissemination activities, listing and explaining the project's priorities, opportunities, internal procedures, and success criteria (KPIs). It also served as a central document to provide common understanding among all project partners, ensuring a coordinated and consistent approach throughout the project's duration.

Deliverable 7.9, closely connected to WP7 and Task 7.2 – Dissemination Activities and Events, is a public report, outlining all dissemination actions carried out throughout the lifetime of the project, from **October 2022 to December 2025**. The report covers scientific and non-scientific publications, participation in conferences and industry events, organisation of demonstration activities and webinars, and the production of videos. It summarises the project's core dissemination messages, key stakeholders, outreach approaches, and the tools and channels employed, while it also provides an evaluation of the reach and effectiveness of the partners' dissemination efforts by comparing the outcomes against the KPIs defined in Deliverable 7.4.

In general, PoDIUM's dissemination efforts exceeded expectations. Partners have participated in 42 conferences and events, delivered overall 49 presentations, published 22 scientific papers, organised 5 webinars, participated in 11 exhibition stands or booths, produced 9 videos, and hosted 3 demonstration events.

1.1. Purpose of the deliverable and intended audience

The aim of this deliverable is to provide a comprehensive summary of all dissemination activities carried out by PoDIUM partners from **October 2022 to December 2025**. It outlines how the consortium shared the project's goals, progress, and results with experts, industry, academia, and the wider CCAM community. In particular, the report offers a detailed overview of PoDIUM's participation in conferences and external events, scientific publications, organisation of demos and webinars, and the videos and communication materials produced during the project's lifecycle. It also reviews the project's dissemination indicators and evaluates performance against the KPIs established in the dissemination strategy.

Deliverable 7.9 is primarily intended for the European Climate, Environment and Infrastructure Executive Agency (CINEA) and the European Commission, as the funding authorities of the PoDIUM project, as well as for the PoDIUM consortium partners. As shown in Table 1 below, it can also be useful

for other EU initiatives and projects, stakeholders involved in CCAM, as well as researchers and everyone interested in PoDIUM’s dissemination approach and outcomes.

Table 1: D7.9 intended audience and reason for interest

Intended audience	Reason for interest
European Commission/CINEA	To read and assess all dissemination activities, verify KPIs, and understand the project’s overall impact, as well as alignment with Horizon Europe goals and objectives.
PoDIUM partners	A comprehensive record of what was done and a useful reference for future communication and exploitation work.
CCAM community	Insights into dissemination practices, scientific outputs, and lessons learned.
Industry and academia stakeholders (OEMs, suppliers, telecom operators, road authorities, RTOs, etc.)	Access to PoDIUM’s technical outcomes and deployment-oriented findings, and information on where these results are available (project website, public deliverables, scientific publications, videos, and Living Lab specific material).
EU Projects, Clusters, and Standardisation Bodies	For comparison, knowledge exchange, and examples that may support their own dissemination planning.
General public and media	To gain a general understanding of what the project is about and how and where its results were communicated.

1.2. Relation to other tasks and deliverables

This deliverable draws on inputs from all PoDIUM work packages, as dissemination activities reflect and communicate their progress and results.

- **WP1 (Project management)** provided project-wide updates, milestones and approved information to be communicated externally, ensuring consistency and appropriate timing across all dissemination outputs.
- **WP2 (Requirements and Specifications)** provided the outline and description of the use cases, requirements, and project information/material used to illustrate PoDIUM’s technical basis in presentations, publications, and website content, and supported the planning and implementation of dissemination and communication activities.
- **WP3 (Technical Innovation and Development)** contributed technical results, innovations, and insights on the project’s technical development progress. These outcomes supported articles, technical talks and dissemination content outlining the projects progress
- **WP4 (Living Lab Integration and Data Collection)** provided perspectives on deployment efforts, integration status, technical preparedness and system operations within the LLs. These contributions informed all dissemination materials related to demonstrations.
- **WP5 (Use Case Evaluation and Demonstration)** provided trial and demonstration outcomes and performance updates. These inputs were used by the WP7 team for event communication, video production, public demonstration material, and final dissemination outputs showcasing the project’s achievements, (i.e. the final webinar and final brochure).

- **WP6 (Business Analysis and CCAM Sustainability Strategy)** offered information on market issues and sustainability factors, guiding dissemination efforts aimed at industry stakeholders.
- **WP7 (Dissemination, Exploitation and International Cooperation)** The deliverable is especially linked to WP7, with Task 7.2 both feeding into and deriving from Task 7.1 on communication strategy and tools and Task 7.3 on liaison activities.

2. Dissemination objectives and overall strategy

PoDIUM’s dissemination efforts adhered to the strategy detailed in Deliverable 7.4 which specified the project’s aims, main messages, key audiences, communication channels and KPIs. The primary objective was to guarantee that PoDIUM’s advancements and outcomes were communicated clearly and uniformly to technical, industrial, academic and general public groups throughout the project duration. As outlined in D7.4 the project aimed to increase awareness, share its work and results with expert groups, strengthen its profile, and broaden its reach via publications, events and demonstration actions. These objectives formed the backbone of the dissemination effort from start to finish.

This chapter provides a summary of the project’s dissemination plan and details its implementation and outcomes. Section [2.1](#) presents the main messages and the target audience, outlining how the project customised communication and dissemination for different groups—industry, institutions, the research community, users, and the general public. Section [2.2](#) describes the variety of communication channels and tools employed throughout the project to disseminate activities and support the promotion of those dissemination efforts. These include all dissemination means, digital channels such as the project’s website, social media, newsletters, and videos, as well as printed materials like roll-up banners, flyers, and posters. Section [2.3](#) looks at how PoDIUM performed against the dissemination KPIs set in Deliverable 7.4. It shows where targets were met or exceeded, including those linked to scientific publications, conference participation, exhibition activities, and communication metrics such as website traffic and social media reach.

2.1. Dissemination main messages and target audience

PoDIUM’s dissemination plan was developed based on a series of messages ([2.1.1](#)) tailored to different key audiences ([2.1.2](#)). The plan outlined in Deliverable 7.4 directed how these messages were formed and distributed, so as to ensure that the project’s objectives, advancements, and findings were conveyed to the groups in a coherent and accessible manner. The aim was to raise awareness of PoDIUM’s work, strengthen its scientific profile, and ensure its findings were accessible to all relevant stakeholders—from technical experts and industry players to policy makers and the general public. Each audience received information suited to its interests and level of technical detail, in order to maximise the impact of the project’s outreach.

2.1.1. Core project messages

To guarantee dissemination across every platform and target group, a series of core dissemination messages was established at the project’s outset and was consistently emphasised throughout the duration of the project. These included:

- **Advancing key technologies in the Physical and Digital Infrastructure (PDI):** PoDIUM reinforces the infrastructure required for future CCAM implementation and growth by enabling connectivity and collaboration, expanding Traffic Management Centres to MEC leveraging MEC to support CCAM services and investigating the possibilities of advanced perception modelling and digital twins.
- **Achieving higher levels of automation and enabling advanced CCAM services:** The project supports Europe’s CCAM activities and ambitions, by building on previous initiatives and funding efforts.

- **Building trust for CCAM:** PoDIUM develops approaches that improve how vehicles and VRUs are integrated into traffic management, ensuring cooperative behaviour in mixed traffic, implementing schemes that support safer interactions with VRUs.
- **Ensuring software reliability and accuracy of CCAM data:** PoDIUM creates techniques for software verification and data validation to maintain CCAM services. Schemes to better integrate vehicles and VRUs in traffic management
- **Demonstrating advanced CCAM use cases in real traffic conditions across three Living Labs (LLs).**

2.1.2. Target audience groups and tailored messaging

The success of PoDIUM’s dissemination relied on the detailed identification and definition of relevant stakeholders and tailored messages to their specific professional interests and needs (Table 2). The following table provides a summary of the identified target groups and their corresponding topics of interest, as initially established in D7.4.

Table 2: PoDIUM target groups and topics of interest

Target Group	Topics of Interest (Main Messages)
Industries (OEMs, MNOs, Telecom, Road/TMC Operators, Suppliers)	CCAM services and multi-connectivity approach; use of 5G mmWave and Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC); new traffic management schemes including data from vehicles and Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs).
Institutions (EC/CINEA, Policy/Decision-Makers, Standardization Bodies)	Acceleration of advanced CCAM services deployment; EU leadership in innovation; recommendations for CCAM technology adoption; PoDIUM reference architecture; and new software integrity methods.
Scientific and Research Community (RTOs, Academia)	Advances in autonomous driving and V2X technologies; deployment activities; new software integrity and data truthfulness methods; and use of 5G mmWave combined with LTE/5G.
Users & General Public (CAV/Conventional Vehicle Users, VRUs, Media)	Large-scale demonstration of 5 Use Cases (UCs) in real traffic conditions; improvement of EU road users’ everyday lives; real-time notifications about emergency cases; and reduced accidents and emissions.

2.2. Dissemination channels and tools

A wide set of dissemination channels and tools (Table 3) were developed and used throughout PoDIUM to support dissemination activities, maintain project visibility, and share results with different stakeholder groups. All materials—from presentations and papers to digital banners and event badges—followed the GA requirements, the European Commission visibility rules, and the project’s brand identity guidelines as defined in [Deliverable 7.1](#) to ensure proper funding acknowledgement and a cohesive representation of the PoDIUM brand.

Table 3: Overview of dissemination channels and examples of activities

Target Audience	Primary Dissemination Channels/Means	Examples of dissemination activities
Industries (OEMs, MNOs, Telecom, Road/TMC Operators, Suppliers)	Trade Shows/Exhibitions (Stands/Booths), Targeted Webinars, Technical Leaflets/Flyers, Partner-specific promotion.	The project hosted or joined exhibition stands and took part in several webinars, both as organiser and contributor. Partners also promoted PoDIUM's use cases at major industry events such as ITS European Congress, the ITS World Congress, EUCAD, and the Smart City Expo World Congress.
Institutions (EC/CINEA, Policy/Decision-Makers, Standardization Bodies)	Dedicated Liaison Activities (Task 7.3), Public Deliverables, Reports, Policy/Strategic Workshops, Exhibitions.	The project took part in joint dissemination activities with other initiatives through meetings, workshops, presentations, and demonstrations. PoDIUM was also featured in CINEA's CCAM brochure, the CORDIS project postcard, and at several CCAM Association events/conferences and final sister project events.
Scientific and Research Community	Scientific Publications (journals, conference proceedings), Zenodo, Conference/Workshop Presentations.	Papers were published in conference proceedings, and several paper presentations were delivered at conferences and events. All public deliverables and research outputs are available in the PoDIUM Zenodo Community .
Users & General Public	Live Demonstration Events, Project Website, Social Media (LinkedIn, X/Twitter), Videos, Press Releases.	Three major public demonstration events were held across the German, Italian, and Spanish Living Labs. These activities were amplified through press releases, videos, and articles produced around each demonstration.

2.2.1. Multimedia and digital outreach

The project used various digital channels and formats to disseminate technical information and document live activities.

The **project website** (<https://podium-project.eu/>) is the main platform for all public information, hosting news, deliverables, publications, demonstration content, and videos. It features dedicated pages for the project's 3 Living Labs (LLs), a news page for dissemination activities and other project updates, and a library containing public deliverables, publications, webinars, promotional materials and other project resources.

Social media channels were used to widen the outreach of updates, promote events, and engage with the CCAM community. These channels enabled distribution of information facilitating direct communication, with key stakeholders.

- **LinkedIn:** ([linkedin.com/company/podium-project-eu](https://www.linkedin.com/company/podium-project-eu)) The PoDIUM Project LinkedIn page was established as the primary professional channel, recognising that it serves as a central social media platform where projects, CCAM experts, EU institutions, and partners actively seek professional news and updates.
- **X/Twitter:** The project initially employed the X/Twitter account ([@PoDIUM_EU](https://twitter.com/PoDIUM_EU)) to share news and interact with relevant stakeholders in real-time, using it for quick communication during events and for important announcements. Over time, the use of the platform decreased as the dissemination strategy was adjusted. Due to uncertainty surrounding the platform following its conversion to X, and based on observed engagement levels, the WP7 team decided to prioritise LinkedIn as a more stable and impactful channel for reaching the project’s target audiences. As a result, the use of the project’s specific hashtag (#PoDIUM_EU) remained slightly below the Year 1 KPI target.
- **YouTube:** The project’s [YouTube channel](#) was created in Month 19 (April 2024) to host PoDIUM’s video content and support the promotion of project activities. It evolved into one of the main social media channels for publishing videos [3.6](#), including the official project video, Living Lab and Use Case videos, and recorded webinars [3.4](#). All videos are arranged into dedicated playlists for easy discovery and sharing. The channel also streamed the live broadcast of UC2 during the final event, allowing participants to follow the technical developments and road situation in real time.

Zenodo Community

In line with the EU’s Open Science directive, the [PoDIUM Zenodo Community](#) was created in M05 (February 2023) to provide open access to all public deliverables, scientific publications, and other publicly available results. In M20, PoDIUM also became one of the first projects to be included in the EU Open Research Repository. Zenodo was also used to upload and share project datasets, ensuring they were accessible under open access alongside the other public results.

Microsoft Teams was the main tool used for hosting webinars and virtual events. Its use ensured reliability, easy access and compliance with EU project requirements. The platform supports secure registration, regulated entry and encrypted communication, offering a GDPR-aligned environment¹ for managing participant data—an essential consideration for an EU-funded project. It also permits tailoring of each webinar: the event page was styled with project graphics, speakers were introduced with personalised profiles, with schedules or resources being modified if needed. Along with smooth presentation sharing, session recording and built-in Q&A and chat features this made Microsoft Teams a practical and reliable option for PoDIUM’s virtual dissemination efforts.

Linktree: A Linktree account was set up by the project to bring all key PoDIUM resources together into a single location. For each of the three demonstration events, Linktree served as a central point where participants could quickly find the agenda, impact assessment for each use case demonstrated (part of Task 5.3), social media links and direct access to the Living Lab pages on the website. The Linktree QR code (Figure 1) was used across PoDIUM’s physical and digital materials—including the final roll-

¹ <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/compliance/regulatory/gdpr?view=o365-worldwide>

up banner, event name badges, yellow vests and digital banners—ensuring consistent visibility and easy access to project information. For the final event in Barcelona, it also hosted the YouTube livestream link so onsite attendees could scan the QR code and jump straight into the session without searching through emails.

Figure 1: PoDIUM Linktree QR code

Infographics: A professional infographic explaining the PoDIUM high-level platform architecture (Figure 2) was produced at the end of Year 1 to help communicate this complex technical topic. Additional digital banners (Figure 3) were also created—using the [Canva platform](#)—for specific purposes such as promoting webinars and demonstration events.

High-level platform architecture

Figure 2: PoDIUM high-level platform architecture infographic

Figure 3: Examples of PoDIUM digital banners

News articles (Figure 4) have been used to disseminate updates about the project to a wide audience. Topics included participation in key external events, promotion of the demonstrations in the Living Lab as well as project webinars, presentation of the partners’ role in the project, and other project-related developments.

Figure 4: PoDIUM news page

Newsletters: Using Mailchimp, a semiannual newsletter was sent out to provide an overview of the project’s latest developments, promote participation in upcoming events, and share the project’s deliverables and publications. Interested stakeholders were invited to sign up using a subscription form available on the project website. The project’s newsletters are available on the website’s library here: <https://podium-project.eu/library/>.

Press Releases: Press releases were used to inform the media of key project milestones, including PoDIUM’s launch, the demonstration held in the German Living Lab, and the project’s Final Event. These were shared to local media outlets to raise awareness of the project activities and generate positive coverage. An additional press release in Greek is planned for January 2026.

2.2.2. Printed dissemination material

Physical materials played an important role in maintaining PoDIUM’s visibility during events and real-world demonstrations. All items are available through the project’s [promotional material](#) library.

Roll-up Banners: A set including four roll-up banners (three general project banners and one dedicated to the Italian Living Lab) were developed. These were used to provide key information and were displayed at conferences, meetings and events.

Flyers and Leaflets: Two main project flyers were developed (an initial and a final version). The initial general leaflet was used throughout the project’s lifetime to promote its objectives, Living Labs and Use Cases, as well as its expected impact, including links to the project website and social media for additional information. A final brochure was produced at the end of the project (Annex – PoDIUM Final Brochure). It provides a clear overview of the project, including the PoDIUM platform architecture, as well as results from the three Living Labs, including a description of each Use Case demonstrated, technical achievements, and challenges and lessons learned for the effective deployment of the project’s technologies.

Posters: A poster presenting key project information was created early (M6).

CORDIS Postcard: The CCAM Association team worked on a portfolio showcasing key information about all CCAM projects, including fiches that are easy to browse and useful for distribution at events and conferences. PoDIUM also had its own CORDIS postcard (Figure 5) which was made available at EUCAD 2025 and at the project’s final event.

Figure 5: PoDIUM CORDIS Postcard

Safety Vests: Yellow safety vests (Figure 6) were produced for all three Living Lab demonstrations to ensure safety and clear project branding on site. They featured the PoDIUM logo, EU funding acknowledgement, and the project’s Linktree QR code. The QR code was updated for each demonstration to highlight the most relevant links, such as use-case questionnaires, agendas, or other event-specific material.

Figure 6: PoDIUM yellow vests

2.3. Achievement of dissemination objectives

The PoDIUM project delivered performance relative to its dissemination Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) achieving and often surpassing the goals specified in Deliverable 7.4. During the entirety of the project, dissemination efforts were systematically recorded through a well-defined internal process and collaborative digital tools. This method ensured transparency and facilitated prompt reporting of all dissemination results. While the qualitative impact of project’s dissemination efforts can be difficult to capture, the KPIs provided a practical framework to monitor progress and assess how effectively the project’s messages reached their intended audiences.

2.3.1. Tracking and Monitoring

Dissemination planning and reporting followed the internal dissemination procedure described in Annex 1 of D7.4, which was shared with and explained to partners early in the project. All partners intending to carry out a dissemination activity—such as participating in an event, submitting a scientific paper, or delivering a presentation—followed an approval procedure overseen by the coordinator (ICCS), Task 7.2 Leader (ICCS) and WP7 Leader (ERTICO).

This procedure ensured that all dissemination activities were aligned with the project’s communication guidelines, brand identity and European Commission requirements, while preventing overlaps or the unintended release of sensitive information. It also supported the efficient monitoring and promotion of dissemination activities throughout the project.

The internal dissemination procedure included:

- **Advance notification:** Partners informed the Task 7.2 Leader before a planned activity, providing key details such as the date, title, target audience, role and a short description. For paper submissions, partners also shared the draft or submitted version so it could be shared

with and reviewed by the consortium. Task 7.2 leader would notify the consortium and ask for feedback, objections or approval.

- **Reporting:** Each activity was recorded in the Dissemination Register (shared Excel file), while all related materials were saved in the project’s collaborative platform, Redmine, under Events, organised by year and by event/publication-specific folders.
- **Documentation:** After completing the activity, partners submitted the final materials (pictures, paper, poster, presentation, press release, etc.) for archiving in Redmine and for publication on the project website or Zenodo, where applicable.

Monthly WP7 meetings and other project coordination calls were used to regularly review and track dissemination activities. To remind partners to follow the dissemination process and to inform them about upcoming opportunities and submission deadlines, regular email reminders were also shared by the dissemination task leader. On Redmine, all content was kept in organised folders (Figure 7) with specific subdirectories for publications, events, and other distribution outputs. This organisation made sure that materials were properly stored, traceable, and easily accessible for reporting and future reference.

Figure 7: Example of a dissemination folder on Redmine

2.3.2. Achievement of Key Dissemination Targets

The initial KPIs and their reported achievement levels (Table 4), covering the full project period, reflect the collective work and dedication of the PoDIUM partners. Overall, the project performed very well against its dissemination targets as most KPIs were met early or clearly exceeded. In particular, PoDIUM met its targets for webinars, non-scientific publications, and the demonstration events organised, while exceeding the KPIs for participation in conferences and events, exhibitions, scientific publications, and video production.

Table 4: Key dissemination targets and achievements

Tools / Channels	KPI Definition	Target (Total)	Achieved	Status
Events	Project events (participants across all demos + final event)	>100	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> German LL Demo: 31 	Met / Exceeded

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Italian LL Demo: 31 Final Event & Spanish LL Demo: 70 	
Conferences & Presentations	Presentations (papers, sessions, workshops, posters)	>30	49	Exceeded
Trade Shows & Exhibitions	Exhibition stands / booths	>3	11	Exceeded
Webinars	Number organised (and ≥50 participants each)	5	5 ≥ 30 – 50 participants	Met
Scientific Publications	Journal & conference papers	>16	22	Met early / Exceeded
Non-Scientific Publications	Trade magazines, press, blogs	>5	8+	Met
Videos	Project + LL demonstration videos	>5	9	Exceeded

2.3.3. Detailed Dissemination Achievements

- Project Events:** PoDIUM’s initial plan foresaw the organisation of four events, including demonstration events in each Living Lab and one final project event. In practice, PoDIUM successfully delivered three public demonstration events: the German Living Lab Demo Day (Ulm – April 2025), the Italian Living Lab Demo Day (Turin – October 2025), and a two-day event in Barcelona that combined the Final Project Event with live demonstrations of the Spanish Living Lab use cases.
- Conferences and Presentations:** The project aimed to achieve over 30 presentations (papers, sessions, workshops, posters) throughout its timeline. PoDIUM partners gave 49 presentations at 42 conferences and events greatly surpassing the KPI.
- Trade Shows and Exhibitions:** The consortium took part in 11 exhibition stands and booths at ITS congresses and Mobility conferences and events throughout Europe, greatly surpassing the goal of 3 exhibitions.
- Webinars:** The KPI required the organisation of 5 webinars by the PoDIUM consortium, with at least 50 participants each. PoDIUM organised 5 webinars, covering the reference architecture, preliminary Living Lab results and final outcomes. Attendance ranged from 30 to 50 participants, and all webinars were uploaded to YouTube, where additional views further increased their reach.
- Scientific Publications:** The goal was to publish overall 16 papers in journals and conference proceedings. By the conclusion of Year 2 (September 2024) 16 conference articles had been already published at conferences including IEEE IV, FUSION and ICTON, achieving the KPI ahead of schedule. By project completion, the consortium had issued 22 peer-reviewed conference papers, all available on the project website and within the PoDIUM Zenodo community.
- Non-scientific publications:** The target for non-scientific publications was met, with more than eight articles published in press and blogs, and more publications and articles expected following the end of the project.
- Videos:** The target was to create more than 5 videos. PoDIUM doubled this output, producing 9 videos showcasing project information, use case details and demonstrations.

2.3.4. Performance of Supporting Communication KPIs

Although the focus of this report is on dissemination KPIs, several related communication indicators (as defined in [Deliverable 7.5](#) Communication Strategy and Plan – Version II) also give a good sense of the project’s visibility and outreach:

- **Website Visits:** Since its launch in February 2023, the project website counted 10,000 visitors, which represents an average of 303 visitors per month. This largely exceeds the target of 150 visitors per month in Year 3, showing strong interest in the project developments, especially in the last year of the project as PoDIUM held its live demonstrations and hosted its Final Event.
- **LinkedIn Followers:** The cumulative target for LinkedIn followers in Year 3 was 150. By February 22, 2024 (M17), the page had already reached 239 followers, significantly exceeding the KPI. By the end of the project in December 2025, the PoDIUM LinkedIn page had grown to 500 followers—more than triple the original target—demonstrating strong engagement throughout the project’s lifetime.
- **News articles:** A total of 54 news items have been published on the project website, surpassing the target of at least 10 news items published each year. This regular flow of project-related updates helped generate interest in the project’s progress and create strong engagement.
- **Newsletters:** PoDIUM sent out 5 newsletters, to a growing audience that counted 52 subscribers in December 2025. A sixth and final newsletter will be sent out in January 2026 with an overview of the project results and resources.
- **Technical leaflets and brochures:** The PoDIUM general leaflet was widely disseminated by project partners at external events – especially exhibitions where PoDIUM participated in - where they allowed the distribution of printed materials, as well as through the project website. In total, more than 60 leaflets have been distributed.

3. Report on Dissemination Activities

This chapter presents an overview of the dissemination activities carried out by the PoDIUM consortium across the project’s duration. All partners contributed to these activities by promoting project results, sharing technical insights, engaging with stakeholders and participating in relevant events at both European and international level. Dissemination actions were recorded through the internal reporting procedure described in chapter [2.3.1](#) and were documented in the project’s Dissemination Register. Partners followed the established workflow to ensure that all activities were reported in a consistent and traceable manner.

As previously noted, throughout the project, PoDIUM participated in **42 conferences and external events** delivering overall **49 presentations**, contributed to **22 scientific publications**, organised **5 webinars**, set up or participated in **11 exhibitions**, produced **9 videos**, and held **3 demonstration events**. The following sections provide a detailed account of these activities, including event and conference participation, exhibition stands, publications, webinars, videos, demonstration events and other dissemination outputs, supplemented with detailed lists, descriptions, visuals and relevant performance metrics.

3.1. Participation in Conferences and Events

PoDIUM’s participation in conferences and events closely matched — and in many cases exceeded — the commitments outlined in the Grant Agreement and the Dissemination Plan (D7.4). The project had committed to organising and participating in conferences, congresses, workshops and networking activities to promote results, seek feedback and engage directly with target stakeholders. Partners were expected to secure speaking opportunities (oral, poster, workshop or special sessions), maintain a presence at major international conferences, and leverage opportunities through partner and EC participation where possible.

Indeed, PoDIUM partners participated in a wide range of conferences and external events throughout the project, to share progress, present results and engage with the wider CCAM community. Each activity was recorded in the Dissemination Register, where partners classified their activity under categories such as a project, session, workshop, paper, poster, webinar, demo or seminar presentation.

In total, PoDIUM participated in **42 conferences and external events**. Following the commitments set out in D7.4, the consortium maintained a strong presence at major industry and scientific gatherings. This includes strong representation at all priority conferences and events listed in D7.4 — such as **ITS European and World Congresses, EUCAD, EuCNC, INFOCOM, ICTON, FUSION, MFI, IEEE IV, IEEE ITSC, and IEEE VTC** - as anticipated in the dissemination strategy.

Across the 42 conferences and events recorded, PoDIUM partners delivered **49 presentations**. These included **11** paper presentations, **14** session presentations (one scheduled), **8** workshop contributions, **6** project presentations, **6** poster presentations, **2** seminar presentations, **1** demo presentation and **1** webinar presentation. In addition to these completed activities, two further contributions are already planned beyond the project’s official reporting period. A session presentation is expected at the RTR Conference 2026 in February, where PoDIUM outcomes will be highlighted within the CCAM

infrastructure session. Furthermore, a paper has been submitted to ITS European Congress 2026, to be held in Istanbul in spring 2026; if accepted, it will add another paper presentation at a major international congress.

The following sections highlight PoDIUM's participation in selected conferences and events [3.1.1](#) and provide a list all external occasions where the project was represented (Table 5), as recorded in the Dissemination Register.

3.1.1. Highlights

As previously mentioned, special effort was made to ensure PoDIUM's presence at major EU and global conferences that attract key audiences in ITS, CCAM and mobility—such as the annual ITS Congresses, EUCAD, IEEE and other events. The primary goal of this effort was to build the project's scientific reputation and maximise its outreach through participation in events and scientific publications. In the sections below are some highlights of PoDIUM's overall participation in these conferences, drawing from activities carried out from October 2022 to September 2025

3.1.1.1. ITS EU and World Congresses

From 2023 to 2025, PoDIUM maintained a strong presence across many ITS European and World Congresses, contributing through session participation, paper presentations, and representation at partners' exhibition stands. Across these events, the project actively engaged with the ITS and CCAM community, showcased its technical developments, and built valuable connections with key stakeholders.

At the [ITS European Congress 2023](#) in Lisbon (22-24 May 2023) the PoDIUM project was invited to present its innovative approach to help accelerate the implementation of CCAM technologies at the European Commission's stand (Figure 8). Alongside the SINFONICA and IN2CCAM projects, which are all part of the CCAM partnership, PoDIUM was highlighted as an example of key drivers for seamless CCAM integration and deployment in Europe. The project was additionally represented at the ERTICO and ITS Hellas booths in the exhibition area.

Figure 8: ITS European Congress 2023 – Lisbon, Portugal

Figure 9: ITS World Congress 2023 – Suzhou, China

At the [ITS World Congress 2023](#), held from 16 to 20 October in Suzhou, China, PoDIUM was represented in Technical Session 17 on Pilots, Trials and Tests of Intelligent and Autonomous Vehicles, where the paper “*The Brenner Motorway as a Living Lab for Testing CCAM*” was presented (Figure 9). The presentation highlighted one of PoDIUM’s Italian Living Lab use cases, demonstrated in a tunnel on the Brenner motorway. It provided an overview of the motorway’s infrastructure, showcasing the advanced services and tools that make it an ideal testing ground for the PoDIUM use case on Risk Management in a Highway Tunnel, aimed at improving traffic monitoring and risk assessment to reduce accidents.

Figure 10: ITS World Congress 2024 - Dubai, UAE

PoDIUM participated in the [ITS World Congress 2024](#) in Dubai (16–20 September), where it highlighted its high-level platform architecture and its contribution to advancing CCAM technologies. In Special Interest Session 59, “*PDI and Communication Developments as CCAM Enablers*”, organised by ICCS and ERTICO (Figure 10), the discussion focused on how communication technologies and physical-digital infrastructure can enhance traffic efficiency and safety. The session emphasised the role of multi-connectivity and robust communication frameworks in supporting the deployment of advanced CCAM services.

At the [ITS European Congress 2025](#) in Seville (19–21 May), the project contributed to three Special Interest Sessions (SIS) offering insights into Vulnerable Road User (VRU) protection, large-scale Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility (CCAM) deployment, and the use of data to improve road safety (Figure 11). In SIS 24 “*Traffic Efficiency and Safety for VRUs and Emergency Response*”, Jorge Suárez Luque (ETRA) presented the Spanish Living Lab use case on emergency vehicle prioritisation and VRU safety in Barcelona. In SIS 64 “*The Way to Safer Roads: Insights into Road Safety and Contributing Factors*”, Daniele Brevi (LINKS) outlined how digital twins enhance VRU protection at intersections in the Italian Living Lab. In SIS 65 “*CCAM: Challenges Towards Large-Scale Deployment*”, Vasilis Sourlas (ICCS) discussed key barriers to scaling CCAM, from operational permissions to technological integration.

Figure 11: ITS European Congress 2025 - Seville, Spain

PoDIUM also participated in the [ITS World Congress 2025](#) in Atlanta (24–28 August), contributing to SIS 66 “Traffic Efficiency and Safety Through CCAM”, organised by the project coordinator ICCS (Figure 12). PoDIUM presented its work on smart traffic control systems, showing how real-time connected vehicle data can support safer and more efficient mobility. Moderated by Dr. Angelos Amditis (PoDIUM Coordinator and Research & Development Director at ICCS), the session brought together speakers from Europe and North America to explore how CCAM and PDI developments can improve mobility around the world.

Figure 12: ITS World Congress 2024 - Atlanta, USA

Last but not least, PoDIUM’s Italian partners have submitted a paper for the upcoming ITS European Congress 2026 in Istanbul (27–29 April), titled *“Trusted Cooperative Perception for Intersection Manoeuvre Assistance for a Connected and Automated Vehicle”*. If accepted, PoDIUM’s presence at ITS congresses will continue even beyond the end of the project.

3.1.1.2. IEEE Conferences

PoDIUM engaged actively with the IEEE research community, targeting leading conferences such as INFOCOM, VTC, ITSC, IV and MFI. These events provided opportunities to disseminate technical results, showcase advancements, and position PoDIUM within the wider CCAM research landscape in Europe and globally.

- IEEE INFOCOM 2023 – the 10th International Workshop on Computer and Networking Experimental Research Using Testbeds (CNERT)** (New York City, USA, May 2023):
 i2CAT presented a demo paper on *“Interoperability between Cellular and V2X Networks (802.11p / LTE-PC5) under a Cloud Native Edge Scenario”*, highlighting early insights into multi-connectivity challenges.
- IEEE IV 2024 – 35th Intelligent Vehicles Symposium** (Jeju Island, South Korea, June 2024):
 UULM partners participated in the [35th IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium](#) (IV 2024) in Jeju, South Korea (Figure 13) and presented PoDIUM through three papers during the poster session: *“Self-Assessment for Multi-Object Tracking Based on Subjective Logic”* (Thomas Griebel), *“Infrastructure-Based Perception with Cameras and Radars for Cooperative Driving Scenarios”* (Alexander Tsaregorodtsev), and *“A Graph Neural Network Approach for Solving the Ranked Assignment Problem in Multi-Object Tracking”* (Robin Dehler). The Ulm University team also took part in side events, including the Women & Young Professionals in ITS (WiE & YP) and Student Activities sessions.

Figure 13: IEEE IV 2024 – Jeju Island, South Korea

- EuCNC 2024 – IEEE ComSoc Sponsored** (Antwerp, Belgium, June 2024):
 A joint paper by UULM, ICCS and UDE, *“The PoDIUM Project and the Role of Communications as a CCAM Enabler”*, was presented, and NOKIA contributed with a session presentation. The session highlighted PoDIUM’s communication-layer innovations as a foundation for CCAM.
- IEEE ITSC 2024 – 27th International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems** (Edmonton, Canada, September 2024):
 As part of the conference, UULM partners presented a total of five papers, three of which were directly related to PoDIUM (Figure 14, Figure 15) These papers focused on novel methods and approaches for the self-assessment of the digital twin developed as part of the project.

Figure 14: IEEE ITSC 2024 – Edmonton, Canada

Figure 15: IEEE ITSC 2024 – Edmonton, Canada

- IEEE VTC 2024-Fall** (Washington, DC, October 2024):
 i2CAT published work on *“MEC Federation for Seamless Service Continuity in Cross-Border Mobility Scenarios”* and on evaluating C-V2X devices, contributing to PoDIUM’s cross-border and multi-connectivity research themes.
- IEEE CAMAD – Session on PDI and Communication Developments as CCAM Enablers** (Athens, Greece, 21 – 23 October 2024)
 Organised by ERTICO and ICCS, this session highlighted opportunities and challenges in interconnecting mobile road users with edge infrastructure and showcased recent advances in distributed and infrastructure-assisted CCAM. Senior experts from industry and academia shared insights from research, pilots and market analysis.
- IEEE SDF & MFI Conference 2023** (Bonn, Germany, 27–29 November 2023)
 PoDIUM presented the paper *“Track Classification for Random Finite Set Based Multi-Sensor Multi-Object Tracking”* in Session 5a, focusing on data fusion and object classification for the Digital Twin. The paper secured the third place for the best student paper award, a recognition honouring the contributions of student researchers in the field.
- IEEE MFI 2024** (Pilsen, Czech Republic, September 2024)
 UULM presented the paper *“An Efficient Implementation of the Fast Product Multi-Sensor Labeled Multi-Bernoulli Filter”* in the Navigation and Tracking session (Figure 16), introducing methods to improve the efficiency of multi-object tracking with multiple sensors.

Figure 16: IEEE MFI 2024 – Pilsen, Czech Republic

- **IEEE MFI 2025** (Texas, USA, September 2025)
UULM partners presented “*ADUULM-TTB: A Scalable, Generic and Efficient Multi-Sensor Multi-Object Tracking Toolbox*”, an open-source framework designed for real-time, scalable multi-sensor multi-object tracking.

3.1.1.3. ICTON

The project achieved visibility at the International Conference on Transparent Optical Networks (ICTON), including invited paper presentations:

- **ICTON 2023** (Bucharest, Romania, July 2023): i2CAT presented a paper on “*Awareness Information Dissemination using Aggregation into Collective Perception Messages for Connected Vehicles*”.
- **ICTON 2024** (Bari, Italy, July 2024): Partners, including UPC, i2CAT, AAE, and ICCS, delivered an Invited Paper Presentation (Figure 17) on “*Real-time responsive Physical and Digital Infrastructure for CCAM-enabled Traffic Management in the Mediterranean cross-border corridor*”

Figure 17: ICTON 2024 – Bari, Italy

3.1.1.4. Road Transport Research results conference (RTR)

The RTR conference is organised jointly by the European Commission ([DGT RTD](#)), the European Road Transport Research Advisory Council ([ERTRAC](#)), [2Zero](#) and the [CCAM Association](#), with the support of [BEPA](#). This annual conference is one of the main platforms for maximising project impact, fostering collaboration across the European research ecosystem, and ensuring research results feed directly into future EU policy and standards development. PoDIUM maintained a presence at the Results from Road Transport Research (RTR) Conference to engage with EU initiatives, namely:

- **RTR Conference 2023** (Brussels, February 2023): The project was introduced during the "Meet Horizon Europe projects" session at the European Commission stand, including the presentation of PoDIUM's CORDIS description on the stand's screen.
- **RTR Conference 2024** (Brussels, February 2024): PoDIUM was presented during a session on "CCAM and connectivity" (Figure 18). ICCS delivered a comprehensive overview of the project's objectives and presented the platform architecture that details the main technical developments to be implemented in the three PoDIUM Living Labs.
- **RTR Conference 2026** (Brussels, February 2026): The project has been invited to the 9th edition of the conference and will present its results during session 30 "Physical and digital CCAM infrastructure", along with the Augmented CCAM, iEXODDUS and FRODDO projects.

Figure 18: RTR Conference 2024 – Brussels, Belgium

3.1.1.5. EUCAD

The consortium leveraged the European Conference on Connected and Automated Driving (EUCAD) for networking and presenting technical infrastructure needs:

- EUCAD 2023** (Brussels, May 2023): PoDIUM participated at [EUCAD 2023](#) with an information stand at the networking exhibition at the Autoworld Museum and co-organised a breakout session titled "*Progressing towards CCAM-hosting and enabling infrastructures*" ([Figure 19](#)). This session addressed digital and physical infrastructure needs for CCAM deployment and involved collaboration with several other CCAM projects.

Figure 19: EUCAD 2023 – Brussels, Belgium

- EUCAD 2025** (Ispra, Italy, May 2025): PoDIUM took part in the [5th EUCAD Conference](#) in Ispra (13–15 May 2025), hosting an exhibition stand alongside Augmented CCAM project (Figure 20) and presenting two demonstrations: the German Living Lab’s multi-connectivity approach for reliable CCAM data transmission, and the Italian Living Lab’s trust and integrity mechanisms for intersection safety (Figure 21). The project also strengthened collaboration within the iCCAM Tech Cluster through meetings with projects such as FRODDO, EVENTS, Althena, CONDUCTOR and iXODDUS. Overall, PoDIUM’s presence highlighted its contributions to advancing PDI technologies and supporting scalable CCAM deployment across Europe.

Figure 20: EUCAD 2025 – Ispra, Italy

Figure 21: EUCAD 2025 – Demo highlights

3.1.2. List of Activities

Table 5: List of presentations in conferences and events

No	Date	Type	Event	Location	Partner(s) involved
Year 1 [M01 - M12] October 2022 - September 2023					
1	22 October 2022	Project Presentation	2nd CCAM Multi-cluster meeting	Brussels, Belgium	ICCS
2	03 May 2023	Session Presentation	EUCAD 2023 <i>'Progressing towards CCAM-hosting and enabling infrastructures'</i>	Brussels, Belgium	ICCS, ERTICO
3	17 – 20 May 2023	Paper Presentation	INFOCOM 2023 (CNERT) <i>'Testbed: Interoperability between native V2X radio technologies (802.11p and LTE-PC5) and cellular V2X over a public 5G network using a MEC based architecture'</i>	NYC, USA	i2CAT
4	22 - 24 May 2023	Project Presentation	ITSEU2023	Lisbon, Portugal	SWARCO, ICCS
5	22 June 2023	Workshop Presentation	DG CONNECT on "Study on the Economic Potential of Far Edge Computing in the Future Smart Internet of Things" <i>'PoDIUM Project Overview'</i>	Online	FSCOM
6	02 – 06 July 2023	Paper Presentation	International Conference on Transparent Optical Networks (ICTON 2023) <i>'Awareness Information Dissemination using Aggregation into Collective Perception Messages for Connected Vehicles'</i>	Bucharest, Romania	i2CAT
7	13 September 2023	Workshop Presentation	ACCAM Pan-European Workshop <i>'The role of communications as a CCAM enabler: Challenges, prospects and the PoDIUM approach'</i>	Riga, Latvia	ICCS
Year 2 [M13 - M24] October 2023 - September 2024					
8	16-20 October 2023	Paper Presentation	ITSWC2023 <i>'The Brenner Motorway as a living lab for testing CCAM'</i>	Suzhou, China	BRE
9	27 - 29 November 2023	Paper Presentation	IEEE SDF-MFI Conference	Bonn, Germany	UULM

			<i>'Track Classification for Random Finite Set Based Multi-Sensor Multi-Object Tracking'</i>		
10	29 November 2023	Workshop Presentation	AWARD Workshop : Charting the Roadmap for Autonomous Vehicles in European Logistics	Online	ICCS
11	7 December 2023	Seminar Presentation	TECoSA Seminar – CCAM Supported by Intelligent Infrastructure <i>Short outlook on the research in the German LL in PoDIUM</i>	Stockholm, Sweden	UULM
12	19 January 2024	Seminar Presentation	Invited Talks on Vision, Graphics, and Speech at Faculty of Information Technology	Brno, Czech Republic	UULM
13	5-7 February 2024	Session Presentation	RTR Conference 2024 Part of the CCAM and Connectivity Session	Brussels, Belgium	ICCS
14	15 - 18 April 2024	Session Presentation	TRA2024 <i>'Multi-connectivity as a technology enabler of advanced CCAM Services'</i>	Dublin, Ireland	ICCS
15	30 May 2024	Workshop Presentation	PDI Workshop <i>'PODIUM –PDI developments and CCAM ecosystem analysis'</i>	Online	ICCS
16	02 - 05 June 2024	Poster Presentation	IEEE IV 2024 <i>'Self-Assessment for Multi-Object Tracking Based on Subjective Logic'</i>	Jeju Island, S. Korea	UULM
17	02 - 05 June 2024	Poster Presentation	IEEE IV 2024 <i>'Infrastructure-based Perception with Cameras and Radars for Cooperative Driving Scenarios'</i>	Jeju Island, S. Korea	UULM
18	02 - 05 June 2024	Poster Presentation	IEEE IV 2024 <i>'A Graph Neural Network Approach for Solving the Ranked Assignment Problem in Multi-Object Tracking'</i>	Jeju Island, S. Korea	UULM
19	03 - 06 June 2024	Session presentation	EUCNC 2024 <i>'5G-Advanced architecture for verticals'</i>	Antwerp, Belgium	NOKIA
20	3 July 2024	Workshop Presentation	Open Network Intelligence for Connected and Autonomous Vehicles (ONI-CAV) Workshop	Catania, Italy	LINKS

			Presentation during Session II: <i>'From research to the road: on ADAS and Connected Car'</i>		
21	07 - 11 July 2024	Paper Presentation	FUSION 2024 <i>'Self-Monitored Clutter Rate Estimation for the Labeled Multi-Bernoulli Filter'</i>	Venice, Italy	UULM
22	14 - 18 July 2024	Paper Presentation	ICTON 2024 <i>'Real-time responsive Physical and Digital Infrastructure for CCAM-enabled Traffic Management in the Mediterranean cross-border corridor'</i>	Bari, Italy	UPC, i2CAT, AAE, IDIADA, CELLNEX, TENALACH, ICCS, MILLA, ENIDE
23	29 July 2024	Session Presentation	ARTS24 conference <i>'PDI connectivity and cooperation enablers building trust and sustainability for CCAM'</i>	San Diego, US (online participation)	ICCS
24	04 - 06 September 2024	Paper Presentation	2024 IEEE International Conference on Multisensor Fusion and Integration (MFI 2024) <i>'An Efficient Implementation of the Fast Product Multi-Sensor Labeled Multi-Bernoulli Filter'</i>	Pilsen, Czech Republic	UULM
25	4-6 September 2024	Paper Presentation	CSUM 2024 <i>'The PDI developments and CCAM ecosystem analysis as per the PoDIUM project'</i>	Karditsa, Greece	ICCS, INCITES
26	16 - 20 September 2024	Session Presentation	ITSWC24 Session presentation on "PDI and communication developments as CCAM enablers"	Dubai	ICCS, UULM, UDE
27	24 September 2024	Project Presentation	CCAM Cluster Event by ROADVIEW	Online	ICCS
28	24 - 27 September 2024	Poster Presentation	IEEE ITSC 2024 <i>'Towards an Advanced Self-Monitoring Tracking Module: Leveraging Statistical Hypothesis Tests and Subjective Logic Reasoning'</i>	Edmonton, Canada	UULM

29	24 - 27 September 2024	Poster Presentation	IEEE ITSC 2024 <i>'Self-Monitored Detection Probability Estimation for the Labeled Multi-Bernoulli Filter'</i>	Edmonton, Canada	UULM
30	24 - 27 September 2024	Poster Presentation	IEEE ITSC 2024 <i>'Self-Assessment and Correction of Sensor Synchronization'</i>	Edmonton, Canada	UULM
Year 3 [M25 - M39] October 2024 – December 2025					
31	07 - 10 October 2024	Paper Presentation	IEEE VTC Fall <i>'MEC Federation for Seamless Service Continuity in Cross- Border Mobility Scenarios'</i>	Washington, DC	i2CAT
32	21 - 23 October 2024	Session Presentation	IEEE CAMAD <i>'PDI (Physical and Digital infrastructure) and communication developments as CCAM (Connected and Cooperative Automated Mobility) enablers'</i>	Athens, Greece	ICCS, ERTICO
33	11 December 2024	Workshop Presentation	Workshop on CCAM Trust Assessment for Safety and Security <i>'Subjective Logic to assess trust in Security and Safety'</i>	Ulm, Germany	UULM
34	25 - 26 March 2025	Workshop Presentation	CONNECT Workshop on Trustworthy AI Presentation on <i>'Data reliability estimation'</i>	Frankfurt, Germany	UULM
35	15 April 2025	Webinar Presentation	ERTICO Focus On Event: Data and AI for Safe and Resilient ITS <i>'Leveraging Data and AI for Traffic Safety and Automated Vehicle Integration'</i>	Online	LINKS
36	14 - 15 May 2025	Demo Presentations	EUCAD 2025 Demo 1 on multi-connectivity for CCAM data transmission Demo 2 UC4/5 of Italian Living Lab: partial demonstration including trust and integrity	Ispra, Italy	ICCS
37	19-21 May 2025	Session Presentation	ITSEU2025 <i>'Traffic efficiency and safety through CCAM: Enhancing PDI for VRUs and emergency response'</i>	Seville, Spain	ICCS, ETRA

38	19 - 21 May 2025	Session Presentation	ITSEU2025 The way to safer roads: insights into road safety and contributing factors	Seville, Spain	LINKS
39	19 - 21 May 2025	Session Presentation	ITSEU2025 CCAM: challenges towards large-scale deployment	Seville, Spain	SWARCO, ICCS
40	10 July 2025	Paper Presentation	FUSION 2025 Online Monitoring for Multi-Object Measurement Model Parameters	Rio De Janeiro, Brazil	UULM
41	11 July 2025	Project Presentation	GAMMS Final Event	Barcelona, Spain	ENIDE, IDIADA
42	24-28 August 2025	Session Presentation	ITSWC2025 <i>'Connected Vehicles, Protected People: Smart Traffic Control in Action'</i>	Atlanta, USA	ICCS, ERTICO
43	2-4 September 2025	Paper Presentation	MFI 2025 <i>'ADUULM-TTB: A Scalable, Generic, and Efficient Multi-Sensor Multi-Object Tracking Toolbox'</i>	Texas, USA	UULM
44	06 October 2025	Project Presentation	SRG CCAM Meeting Presentation of Horizon Europe projects	Athens, Greece	ICCS
45	08 October 2025	Workshop Presentation	Urban CCAM Mapping and planning	Brussels, Belgium	ICCS
46	4 November 2025	Session Presentation	SCEWC2025 PoDIUM UC2 Presentation	Barcelona, Spain	ETRA
47	26 November 2025	Project Presentation	FRODDO 3 rd General Assembly PoDIUM Project Overview	Athens, Greece	ICCS, ERTICO
48	04 December 2025	Session Presentation	IRF 2025 Annual Conference Presentation during session: <i>'Digital and Automated: The Next Era of Roads'</i>	Online	ETRA
2026					
49	12 February 2026	Session Presentation	RTR Conference 2026 Presentation during Session on Physical and digital CCAM infrastructure	Brussels, Belgium	ICCS
-	27-29 April, 2026	Paper submission - tbd	ITSEU2026 <i>'Trusted Cooperative Perception for Intersection Manoeuvre Assistance for a</i>	Istanbul, Turkey	SWARCO, LINKS, TIM, CRF

			<i>Connected and Automated Vehicle'</i>		
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3.2. Exhibition stands and booth participation

PoDIUM partners kept a strong presence at major European and local exhibitions, trade fairs and congresses to provide information about the project, showcase project developments, demonstrate Living Lab results and engage directly with stakeholders. The KPI set in D7.4 required participation in at least 3 exhibitions over the project's duration. This target was significantly exceeded, with PoDIUM partners participating in **11 exhibitions** and booth activities between 2023 and 2025 (Figure 22). Table 6 below summarises all exhibition activities as reported in the Dissemination Register.

Table 6: Exhibition stands and booth participation

No	Date	Event	Location	Type of Participation	Partner(s)
1	03–04 May 2023	EUCAD 2023	Brussels	Information stand	ICCS
2	22–24 May 2023	ITS Lisbon 2023	Lisbon, Portugal	ERTICO stand & ITS Hellas booth	ICCS, ERTICO
3	2–5 April 2024	Connecting Europe Days	Brussels	Joint booth with EVENTS & ENVELOPE	ICCS
4	18 April 2024	EUCAD 2024	Dublin, Ireland	Roll-up during CCAM Networking Reception	ICCS
5	05–06 June 2024	ITS Hellas 2024	Athens, Greece	Video presentation & flyers	ICCS
6	16–20 September 2024	ITSWC2024	Dubai, UAE	Display on ERTICO stand & flyers	ERTICO, ICCS
7	07–08 May 2025	ITS Hellas 2025	Athens, Greece	Video presentation & flyers	ICCS
8	13–15 May 2025	EUCAD 2025	Ispra, Italy	1 information stand + 1 booth	ICCS, German & Italian LL partners
9	30 June – 02 July 2025	International Symposium 'Navigating the Future of Traffic Management'	Athens, Greece	Video and flyers on the ICCS/NTUA stand	ICCS
10	22 October 2025	IN2CCAM / CONDUCTOR Final Event	Brussels	Banner and short presentation	ERTICO, ICCS
11	04–06 November 2025	Smart City Expo World Congress 2025	Barcelona, Spain	Video & presentation	ETRA, BCN

Figure 22: PoDIUM in Exhibitions

3.3. Publications

In D7.4, PoDIUM committed to disseminating its research results through peer-reviewed scientific channels, including both conference proceedings and journal publications. The project successfully delivered a substantial body of peer-reviewed work through international conference papers—an output that is highly relevant in fast-moving fields such as CCAM, wireless communications and cooperative perception, where conferences are often the primary place for publishing emerging research.

Over the duration of the project, the consortium produced **22 scientific publications** in peer-reviewed conference proceedings, as well as **one thesis dissertation** based on PoDIUM research, surpassing the KPI set for 16 scientific publications. Although no journal publications were published within the project period, several partners have indicated that their work is now reaching journal-ready maturity.

Manuscripts have already been submitted to journals such as IEEE Intelligent Transportation Systems Magazine (ITSM) and IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Vehicles (T-IV), with additional submissions expected after the project’s completion.

The complete list of PoDIUM scientific publications is presented in the table below (Table 7), including the publication date, paper title, conference venue, contributing partners and authors. Full publication records and the open-access versions can be found on the [PoDIUM website’s Publications page](#) and within the [PoDIUM Zenodo community](#), which serves as the central repository for all publicly accessible project outputs.

Table 7: List of publications

No	Date of Publication	Title	Journal/Conference	Partner(s) Involved	Authors
Year 1 [M01 - M12] October 2022 - September 2023					
1	17 - 20 May, 2023	Demo: Interoperability between Cellular and V2X Networks (802.11p / LTE-PC5) under a Cloud Native Edge Scenario	The 10th International Workshop on Computer and Networking Experimental Research Using Testbed (INFOCOM 2023)	i2CAT	Marias-i-Parella, J., Pino, A., Cordero, B., Casademont, J., Carmona-Cejudo, E., & Vázquez-Gallego, F.
2	2 - 6 July 2023	Awareness Information Dissemination using Aggregation into Collective Perception Messages for Connected Vehicles	International Conference on Transparent Optical Networks (ICTON 2023)	I2CAT	J. M. i. Parella, J. Casademont, F. Vázquez-Gallego and E. Lopez-Aguilera
3	26 July 2023	On Data Plane Multipath Scheduling for Connected Mobility Applications	Workshop on Modeling, Analysis and Simulation of Next-Generation Communication Networks	UDE	M. Herrmann, A. Rizk
Year 2 [M13 - M24] October 2023 - September 2024					
4	16 -20 October 2023	The Brenner Motorway as a living lab for testing CCAM	ITSWC2023	BRE	C. Costa, I. De Biasi
5	27 - 29 November 2023	Track Classification for Random Finite Set Based Multi-Sensor Multi-Object Tracking	IEEE SDF-MFI Conference	UULM	A. Scheible, T. Griebel, M. Herrmann, C. Hermann, M. Buchholz
6	02 - 05 June 2024	Self-Assessment for Multi-Object Tracking Based on Subjective Logic	IEEE IV 2024	UULM	Thomas Griebel, Nikolas Dehler, Alexander Scheible, Michael

					Buchholz, Klaus Dietmayer
7	02 - 05 June 2024	Infrastructure-based Perception with Cameras and Radars for Cooperative Driving Scenarios	IEEE IV 2024	UULM	Alexander Tsaregorodtsev, Michael Buchholz, and Vasileios Belagiannis
8	02 - 05 June 2024	A Graph Neural Network Approach for Solving the Ranked Assignment Problem in Multi-Object Tracking	IEEE IV 2024	UULM	Robin Dehler, Martin Herrmann, Jan Stroheck, and Michael Buchholz
9	03 - 06 June 2024	The PoDIUM project and the role of communications as a CCAM enabler	EuCNC 2024	UULM, ICCS, UDE	Marcel Kern, Markus Wimmer, Michael Buchholz, Alexander Scheible, Lazaros Gkatzikis, Vasilis Sourlas, Amr Rizk, Tobias Müller
10	07 - 11 July 2024	Self-Monitored Clutter Rate Estimation for the Labeled Multi-Bernoulli Filter	FUSION 2024	UULM	Alexander Scheible, Thomas Griebel, and Michael Buchholz
11	14 - 18 July 2024	Real-time responsive Physical and Digital Infrastructure for CCAM-enabled Traffic Management in the Mediterranean cross-border corridor	ICTON2024	UPC, i2CAT, AAE, IDIADA, CELLNEX, TENALACH, ICCS, MILLA, ENIDE	Jordi Casademont (UPC), Jordi Marias-i-Parella (i2CAT), Harilaos Vasiliadis (AAE), Jacint Castells (IDIADA), William Diego (CELLNEX), Aristarco Tomas (TENALACH), Lazaros Gkatzikis (ICCS)
12	04 - 06 September 2024	An Efficient Implementation of the Fast Product Multi-Sensor Labeled Multi-Bernoulli Filter	MFI2024	UULM	Charlotte Hermann, Alexander Scheible, Michael Buchholz, and Klaus Dietmayer
13	4-6 September 2024	The PDI developments and CCAM ecosystem analysis as per the PoDIUM project	CSUM 2024	ICCS, INCITES	Lazaros Gkatzikis, Ioannis Neokosmidis, Theodoros Rokkas and Vasilis Sourlas

14	24 - 27 September 2024	Towards an Advanced Self- Monitoring Tracking Module: Leveraging Statistical Hypothesis Tests and Subjective Logic Reasoning	IEEE ITSC 2024	UULM	Thomas Griebel, Alexander Scheible, Michael Buchholz, Klaus Dietmayer
15	24 - 27 September 2024	Self-Monitored Detection Probability Estimation for the Labeled Multi- Bernoulli Filter	IEEE ITSC 2024	UULM	Alexander Scheible, Thomas Griebel, Michael Buchholz
16	24 - 27 September 2024	Self-Assessment and Correction of Sensor Synchronization	IEEE ITSC 2024	UULM	Thomas Wodtko, Alexander Scheible, Michael Buchholz
Year 3 [M25 - M39] October 2024 – December 2025					
17	07 - 10 October 2024	Evaluation of C-V2X devices to deploy a C-ITS information distributor system based on a V2I2V architecture	IEEE VTC2024-Fall	i2CAT	Lluc Feixa- Morancho, Pau Feixa-Morancho, Marc Codina, Jordi Marias-i-Parella, Jordi Casademont, Bruno Cordero, Francisco Vazquez-Gallego, Jesus Alonso- Zarate
18	14 March 2025	Enhancing Safety and Efficiency for Vulnerable Road Users: Design and Evaluation of a Mobile User Interface for Cooperative Maneuver Coordination	(Thesis/Dissertation)	NOKIA, UULM	Deniz Karagöz
19	06 August 2025	Adaptive Minimal Latency In-Sequence Ordering for Multi- Channel Data Fusion in Autonomous Driving	36th IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium (IV)	UULM	Thomas Wodtko, Alexander Scheible, Dominik Authaler and Michael Buchholz
20	26 August 2025	Online Monitoring for Multi-Object Measurement Model Parameters	FUSION 2025	UULM	Alexander Scheible and Michael Buchholz

21	2 – 4 September 2025	ADUULM-TTB: A Scalable, Generic, and Efficient Multi-Sensor Multi-Object Tracking Toolbox	MFI 2025	UULM	Alexander Scheible, Charlotte Hermann, Thomas Griebel, Michael Buchholz, and Klaus Dietmayer
22	10 - 12 November 2025	A Multiobjective DQN Framework for Dynamic Service Orchestration in the Computing Continuum	IEEE NFV SDN 2025	ICCS	Paris Flegkas, Antonis Tseos, Vasilis Sourlas, Angelos Amditis

3.4. Articles and non-scientific publications

Non-scientific publications also played an important role in communicating PoDIUM’s activities and results beyond the research community. [Table 8](#) provides an overview of a selected sample of non-scientific publications and articles on PoDIUM published on partners’ websites and other communication channels. Beyond these examples, partners disseminated PoDIUM-related news and results more broadly through additional articles, project updates, and social media channels throughout the project.

Table 8: Articles and non-scientific publications

No	Type	Title	Partner	Year	Link
1	Article	PoDIUM – A new CCAM project coordinated by ISENSE Group kicked-off in Athens	ICCS	2022	https://i-sense.iccs.gr/news/podium-a-new-ccam-project-coordinated-by-isense-group-kicked-off-in-athens/
2	Article	PoDIUM accelerates the implementation of CCAM technology	ERTICO	2023	https://erticonetwork.com/podium-accelerates-the-implementation-of-ccam-technology/
3	Article	Vernetzte, kooperative und automatisierte Mobilität Europäisches Netzwerk PoDIUM soll Einführung beschleunigen	UULM	2023	https://www.uni-ulm.de/in/fakultaet/in-detailseiten/news-detail/article/vernetzte-kooperative-und-automatisierte-mobilitaet-europaeisches-netzwerk-podium-soll-einfuehrung-beschleunigen/
4	Brochure	Towards Cooperative, Connected and	ALL	2023	https://podium-project.eu/podium-featured-in-cineas-new-brochure/

		Automated Mobility			
5	Article	Automated mobility starts with physical and digital infrastructure	ALL	2025	https://cordis.europa.eu/article/id/457152-automated-mobility-starts-with-physical-and-digital-infrastructure
6	Article	Auch automatisierte Fahrzeuge können kooperieren Demo-Event des PoDIUM-Projekts zum vernetzten kooperativen Fahren	UULM	2025	https://www.uni-ulm.de/in/fakultaet/in-detailseiten/news-detail/article/auch-automatisierte-fahrzeuge-koennen-kooperieren-demo-event-des-podium-projekts-zum-vernetzten-kooperativen-fahren/
7	Article	PoDIUM concludes after three years of innovation in connected and automated driving	ERTICO	2025	https://ertico.com/podium-concludes-after-three-years-of-innovation-in-connected-and-automated-driving
8	Article	PoDIUM Final Event: Advancing Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility through Smart Infrastructure	ICCS	2025	https://i-sense.iccs.gr/news/podium-final-event-advancing-connected-cooperative-and-automated-mobility-through-smart-infrastructure/

3.5. Webinars

PoDIUM committed to organising at least five webinars addressing different topics and stakeholder groups, targeting at least 50 participants for each event. The consortium has organised 5 webinars throughout the project duration (Table 9).

Table 9: PoDIUM webinars

No	Title / Topic	Planned Date	Partners Involved	Attendees	YouTube Views
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1	A multi-connectivity approach for CCAM Services: PoDIUM's architecture platform	30 November 2023	ICCS, UULM, UDE, ETRA, LINKS	48	20
2	The Spanish Living Lab and Its Use Cases: Progress and Challenges to Date	27 November 2024	AAE, ETRA, IDIADA	33	35
3	The German Living Lab in the PoDIUM Project: Preliminary Results from the Use Case 'Cooperative Corridor Management in the City of Ulm involving Multi-connectivity'	3 December 2024	UULM, NOKIA, UDE, BOSCH	42	37
4	Description of the Italian LL and UCs: Integration and Preliminary Results	30 January 2025	CRF	34	35
5	PoDIUM wrap-up webinar: Project results and the road ahead	17 December 2025	ICCS, AAE, ETRA, CRF, BOSCH, UULM	29	20

The webinars were designed to follow the project phases. The first webinar in 2023 introduced the PoDIUM common reference architecture, and as work in the Living Labs progressed, webinars 2, 3 and 4 — held in 2024 and early 2025 — presented developments in the German, Spanish and Italian Living Labs, outlining their Use Cases, technical challenges and early lessons learned. The final wrap-up webinar (No. 5) that took place in the last month of the project, presented the project's concluding results from all three Living Labs, and provided some insights on public acceptance of the platform and the overall impact of the PoDIUM solution.

3.5.1. Webinar 1 – A Multi-Connectivity Approach for CCAM Services: PoDIUM's Architecture Platform

Held on 30 November 2023, this first webinar introduced PoDIUM's high-level architecture, covering communication, data management, and trust mechanisms forming the basis of the Living Lab developments (Figure 23). Delivered by ICCS, UULM, UDE, ETRA and LINKS partners, it attracted 48 participants and has 20 views on YouTube so far.

Agenda:

- [Short Introduction to the project](#) – Lazaros Gkatzikis
- [The PoDIUM Platform Architecture](#) – Michael Buchholz
- [PoDIUM Communication View](#) – Amr Rizk
- [Functional view, Data flow and Storage](#) – Jorge Suárez
- [Data truthfulness & Software integrity](#) – Guido Gavilanes
- [Q&A session](#)

Link: <https://podium-project.eu/podium-webinar-a-multi-connectivity-approach-for-ccam-services-podiums-architecture-platform/>

Figure 23: PoDIUM 1st Webinar – PoDIUM’s Architecture Platform

3.5.2. Webinar 2 – The Spanish Living Lab and Its Use Cases: Progress and Challenges to Date

On 27 November 2024, the second webinar spotlighted the Spanish Living Lab (Figure 24), presenting advancements in user-centric traffic management and cross-border highway operation. Delivered by ETRA AAE, IDIADA and ICCS, it gathered 33 participants and has 35 views on YouTube.

Agenda:

- [Introduction to PoDIUM](#) – Giorgos Zacharopoulos (ICCS)
- [PDI for User-Centric Traffic Management in Urban Corridors with High Priority Vehicles and Vulnerable Road Users \(VRUs\)](#) – Jorge Suárez Luque (ETRA)
- [Real-Time Responsive PDI for CCAM in the Mediterranean Cross-Border Corridor](#) – Harilaos Vasiliadis & David Porcuna (Abertis Autopistas)
- [C-V2X Communication](#) – Jacint Castells Fontelles (Applus+ IDIADA)

Link: <https://podium-project.eu/a-recap-of-the-podium-spanish-living-lab-webinar/>

Figure 24: PoDIUM 2nd Webinar – Spanish Living Lab

3.5.3. Webinar 3 – The German Living Lab: Preliminary Results from the Use Case “Cooperative Corridor Management in the City of Ulm”

Held on 3 December 2024, this session showcased early results from the German Living Lab (Figure 25) including multi-connectivity, cooperative manoeuvre planning and trusted digital twin applications. Delivered by UULM, NOKIA, UDE and BOSCH partners, it reached 42 participants and has 37 views on YouTube.

Agenda:

- [Introduction to the German Living Lab and Use Case](#) – Priv.-Doz. Dr.-Ing. Michael Buchholz (Ulm University)
- [Usage of 5G mmWave for CCAM](#) – Steffen Schulz (Nokia)
- [Multi-Connectivity based adaptive Data Traffic Steering for Cooperative Corridor](#) – Prof. Dr.-Ing. Amr Rizk (University Duisburg-Essen)
- [Trust Building for Data Sources of a Digital Twin](#) – Alexander Scheible (Ulm University)
- [Functional Design of the Cooperative Maneuver Planner](#) – Christian Eilers (Bosch)

Link: <https://podium-project.eu/highlights-from-the-podium-german-living-lab-webinar/>

Figure 25: PoDIUM 3rd Webinar – German Living Lab

3.5.4. Webinar 4 – Description of the Italian Living Lab and Use Cases: Integration and Preliminary Results

On 30 January 2025, the fourth webinar presented the Italian Living Lab’s work on VRU protection in urban spaces and risk management in highway tunnels (Figure 26). Presented by LINKS, TIM, SWARCO, Stellantis-CRF and BRE, it recorded 34 participants and 35 views on YouTube.

Agenda:

- Introduction (context and objectives)
 - PODIUM Project
 - The Italian Living Lab
- UC4
 - 5G Network and Enablers
 - PODIUM Platform
 - Connected and Automated Vehicle
 - OBU: Integrity and VRUs
- UC5
 - A22 Tunnel
 - Connected and automated driving in tunnel
 - RSU

Link: <https://podium-project.eu/key-takeaways-from-the-podium-italian-living-lab-webinar/>

Figure 26: PoDIUM 4th Webinar - Italian Living Lab

3.5.5. Webinar 5 – PoDIUM Wrap-Up Webinar: Project results and the road ahead

Scheduled for 17 December 2025, the final webinar (Figure 27) brought together ICCS, UULM, ETRA, AAE, LINKS, CRF, and all partners to present PoDIUM’s overall results, offering a concise wrap-up of the project’s work, results, and insights since its launch in 2022. The webinar summarised performance, results, challenges, and lessons learned across the PoDIUM Living Labs in Germany, Italy, and Spain, as well as insights from all five use cases. It also covered the project’s market outlook and technical–economic analysis, highlighting how PoDIUM’s solutions fit within the evolving CCAM and PDI landscape.

Agenda:

- Welcome Notes, Sevi Christoforou – ICCS
- Project Overview, Georgios Zacharopoulos – ICCS
- Use Case deep-dive
 - UC1 Cooperative Corridor Management in the City of Ulm
Michael Buchholz -Ulm University
 - UC2 Physical and Digital Infrastructure (PDI) for a User-Centric, CCAM-enabled Traffic Management in Urban Corridors with High Priority Vehicles and Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs), Jorge Suárez Luque - ETRA
 - UC3 Real-time responsive PDI for CCAM-enabled Traffic Management in the Mediterranean Cross-Border Corridor, Harilaos Vasiliadis, AAE
 - UC4 Trusted Cooperative Perception for Intersection Manoeuvre Assistance, Filippo Visintainer - Stellantis – CRF & Guido Gavilanes - LINKS Foundation
 - UC5 Risk Management in a Highway Tunnel. Paolo Faccin - Autostrada del Brennero
- Business insights & sustainability of PoDIUM results, Ioannis Neokosmidis - INCITES

Link: <https://youtu.be/JTrL0qDTTOK>

Agenda

Welcome
Sevi Christoforou - ICCS

Project Overview
Georgios Zacharopoulos – ICCS

Use Case deep-dive

- **UC1 Cooperative Corridor Management in the City of Ulm**
Michael Buchholz (Ulm University)
- **UC2 Physical and Digital Infrastructure (PDI) for a User-Centric, CCAM-enabled Traffic Management in Urban Corridors with High Priority Vehicles and Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs)**
Jorge Suárez Luque (ETRA)
- **UC3 Real-time responsive PDI for CCAM-enabled Traffic Management in the Mediterranean Cross-Border Corridor**
Harilaos Vasiladis (AAE)
- **UC4 Trusted Cooperative Perception for Intersection Manoeuvre Assistance**
Filippo Visintainer (Stellantis - CRF) & Guido Gavilanes (LINKS Foundation)
- **UC5 Risk Management in a Highway Tunnel**
Paolo Faccin (Autostrada del Brennero) & Filippo Visintainer

Business insights & sustainability of PoDIUM results
Ioannis Neokosmidis (INCITES)

Sevi Christoforou

Sevi Christoforou

Jorge Suárez Luque

Guido Gavilanes

FILIPPO VI... Harilaos V...

Ioannis Ne... Faccin Paolo

Giorgos Z... Michael B...

David Q...

Figure 27: PoDIUM 5th Webinar - PoDIUM Wrap-up

3.6. Videos

PoDIUM initially planned to produce five videos over the project duration. This target was significantly exceeded, with a total of **nine videos** delivered. The expanded video portfolio played an important role in communicating technical results, showcasing demonstrations and supporting the project’s visibility across events, exhibitions and online channels.

3.6.1. Official Project Video and Living Lab Clips

The [main animated project video](#) was produced in M19 (April 2024) and introduced PoDIUM’s overall scope, Living Labs and Use Cases. Designed with subtitles and descriptive visuals, it was well suited for exhibition environments where sound is often unavailable. To complement it, three short versions were produced—each dedicated to one of the Living Labs—allowing viewers to quickly grasp site-specific goals and scenarios.

3.6.2. Demo Day Videos

Four videos captured PoDIUM’s demonstration activities in real traffic or controlled environments across the Living Labs:

1. **German Living Lab Demo Day** (April 2025): Showcased the “Cooperative Corridor Management” use case in Ulm, including a scenario where Connected and Automated Vehicles synchronise movements to safely navigate a blocked lane on a two-lane road.
Link: <https://youtu.be/TCNMT-wheVo?si=-b9PpYY9WHpo5kD->
2. **Italian Living Lab Demo Day & UC4 Video** (October 2025): Presented demonstrations in Turin highlighting VRU protection at intersections and risk management in tunnels. The video also featured the live execution of UC4, and the hardware used in the Living Lab.
Link: <https://youtu.be/YRULxO7xm10?si=fuQpzWwG7WWMiQwUg>
3. **Final Event & UC2/UC3 Demonstrations (Barcelona)** (November 2025): Documented the project’s closing event and the live demonstration of emergency vehicle prioritisation and VRU

protection in Gran Via Avenue in Barcelona. It also offered a short overview of the cross-border traffic management demonstration at Autopistas' Future Road Lab and C-32.

Link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5Z3lhBGndL0>

3.6.3. Use Case Videos

In addition to the demo event coverage, PoDIUM produced shorter technical videos illustrating the core functionality of each of the Living Lab Use Cases:

4. UC1 – **PoDIUM German Living Lab: Cooperative Corridor Management in the City of Ulm**
Link: <https://youtu.be/wMX0YBbjGDQ>
5. UC2 – **Emergency vehicle prioritisation and VRU protection in Barcelona**
Link: <https://youtu.be/IJtLL42DtZA>
6. UC3 – **Real-time responsive PDI for CCAM-enabled traffic management in cross-border corridors**
Link: <https://youtu.be/FPET2lt2aCU>
7. UC5 – **PoDIUM Italian Living Lab: Risk Management in a Highway Tunnel**
Link: <https://youtu.be/XqMWfzW6rK0>
8. **Passenger App Video** – Demonstrating the VRU-focused mobile application and route-sharing functionality used for risk assessment in the Italian Living Lab.
Link: <https://youtu.be/Ui2gVB1U8cA>

3.7. Demonstration Events

The live demonstration events organised by the PoDIUM project were an integral part of the overall dissemination plan, designed to demonstrate the project's rich set of 5 CCAM UCs (further detailed into multiple individual scenarios) in real traffic conditions. PoDIUM planned for and conducted a total of 3 demonstration events in the project's 3 Living Labs in Ulm, Germany, Turin, Italy and Barcelona, Spain (Figure 28), showcasing real-world demonstrations, in addition to the Final Event.

Figure 28: PoDIUM three Living Labs and demonstration venues

3.7.1. Preparation and coordination for demonstration events

To ensure success and maximise the impact of the demonstration events, the organisation involved a preparation procedure managed collaboratively between the Living Lab (LL) leaders, the coordinator

(ICCS) and the Work Package 7 (WP7) team, specifically Task 7.2 (Dissemination activities and events). The main goal of this coordinated approach was to determine event details, facilitate organisation, and ensure optimum success across the three diversified Living Labs.

3.7.1.1. Internal preparation and meetings

WP7 established a structured coordination framework and a dedicated planning presentation was developed and used as a practical checklist outlining requirements, responsibilities, and the overall dissemination and promotion plan for each event. This presentation was shared with the respective Living Lab leaders well in advance of each demonstration and supported through regular coordination calls between the coordinator, the WP7 team and the Living Lab/UC leaders.

The preparation plan defined the key dissemination actions to be implemented at local and project level in order to maximise the impact of each demonstration. These actions included the definition of core event details (date, location, agenda and complementary activities), the identification and invitation of relevant stakeholders, the preparation and distribution of press releases in both English and the local language, targeted promotion through social media and online channels, and the development of complementary communication materials in close collaboration with the Task 7.1 Leader (i.e. yellow vests, car stickers, etc.).

Within this framework, WP7 coordinated and supported all dissemination activities by leading the preparatory calls with each Living Lab, drafting articles and announcements for the PoDIUM website, creating digital material, promoting content through PoDIUM’s social media, the ICCS and ERTICO newsletters, as well as mailing campaigns. WP7 also prepared press releases in English, identified international media outlets, provided video, photo and marketing support, produced follow-up articles, and created dedicated pages on the PoDIUM website hosting videos and related materials (Figure 29).

Figure 29: Demonstration preparation slide - WP7 team

In parallel, the Living Lab partners ensured effective local implementation by keeping ICCS and ERTICO informed about programme updates, organising presentations to showcase trial results and collect

feedback, promoting the events through their corporate communication channels, sharing content from PoDIUM social media accounts, preparing press releases in the local language when needed, inviting relevant stakeholders and local press, administering user acceptance questionnaires, and providing support to the WP7 in organisational issues (Figure 30).

WP7: Communication requirements & responsibilities

Living Lab Partners

Action Point
Keep ICCS & ERTICO up-to-date about event programme, participation and updates
Organise associated workshops/presentations to present the trials results/ comment the demos and collect feedback/ input
Use corporate promotional channels to promote the event
Share posts from PoDIUM accounts
Press release in local language (assist with the English version)
Identification and invitation of relevant stakeholders & local press
Circulate User Acceptance questionnaires
Organise pictures and videos on-site in collaboration with the WP7 team: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> For promotion after the event Live stream or pre-recorded videos during the event

Figure 30: Demonstration preparation slide - Living Lab leaders

3.7.2. German Living Lab Demo Day in Ulm

The German Living Lab demonstrated the use case “Cooperative Corridor Management in the City of Ulm”, demonstrating how cooperative local traffic management can improve safety and efficiency in complex urban traffic scenarios. Two situations were tested on a two-lane road: a lane blockage requiring coordinated manoeuvres between Connected and Automated Vehicles (CAVs), and a mixed-traffic scenario where a cyclist connected via a smartphone replaced one of the CAVs.

The demonstration took place at a pilot site near Ulm University, equipped with advanced sensing and multi-connectivity infrastructure, including 5G mmWave, MEC, scheduling software, and a Digital Twin to support reliable operation. Led by Ulm University with Bosch, Nokia, and the University of Duisburg-Essen, the demonstration event was held on 9 April and included live demonstration drives and technical discussions. Further details on the setup, scenarios, and outcomes are provided in Table 10 below.

Table 10: German Living Lab demonstration details

Living Lab	German Living Lab
Date	09 April 2025
Demo Site	Ulm University & test junction in Ulm-Lehr (Mähringer Str./Loherstr.)

<p>Agenda</p>	<p>09:00 – 09:30 Arrival / Registration 09:30 – 09:40 Welcome, Agenda Overview (ICCS, UULM) 09:40 – 10:10 UC1 Overview (UULM) 10:10 – 10:30 Tour at Institute MRM @ UULM 10:30 – 11:00 Transfer to pilot site (public transport) 11:00 – 12:00 On-site live demos 12:00 – 12:30 Transfer back to UULM 12:30 – 13:15 Lunch break 13:15 – 14:45 Technical Talks (German LL Partners)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Mobile Communication in UC1 with a focus on Usage of 5G mmWave 2. Adaptive Data Routing in Networks using the Multi-Connectivity Scheduler 3. UC1 Server Environment Model with Trust Building <p>14:45 – 15:15 Coffee Break 15:15 – 16:15 Technical Talks (German LL Partners)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Cooperative Maneuver Planning for ad hoc Corridor Management 5. Function Offloading at the German LL : Moving Perception into the Edge <p>16:15 – 16:45 Further UC1 steps (German LL Partners) 16:45 – 17:00 Wrap-up and Outlook on further Demos (ICCS)</p>
<p>Use Case(s) in focus and demonstrated scenario(s)</p>	<p>UC1 – Cooperative Corridor Management The central element of the live demonstration was a complex scenario designed to test how automated vehicles coordinate smoothly in intricate traffic situations. The scenario involved:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A road lane being blocked by a stationary vehicle (the obstacle). • Two automated vehicles approaching from opposite directions needing to execute a cooperative maneuver to pass the obstruction. • The crucial cooperative step: the oncoming vehicle, which typically holds the right of way in a conventional scenario, must yield to the vehicle stuck behind the obstruction to maintain traffic flow in the blocked lane.
<p>Main outcome</p>	<p>Successful validation of cooperative behaviour in a complex urban traffic</p>
<p>Partners Involved</p>	<p>Ulm University, BOSCH, NOKIA, and the University of Duisburg-Essen (UDE)</p>
<p>Participants</p>	<p>31 participants (closed event - internal)</p>

Press Release/articles	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. (DE) https://www.uni-ulm.de/in/fakultaet/in-detailseiten/news-detail/article/auch-automatisierte-fahrzeuge-koennen-kooperieren-demo-event-des-podium-projekts-zum-vernetzten-kooperativen-fahren/ 2. (EN) https://www.uni-ulm.de/en/in/faculty-of-engineering-computer-science-and-psychology/in-detailseiten/news-detail/article/auch-automatisierte-fahrzeuge-koennen-kooperierendemo-event-des-podium-projekts-zum-vernetzten-kooperativen-fahren/ 3. https://podium-project.eu/podiums-german-living-lab-demonstrates-cooperative-corridor-management/
German LL web page	https://podium-project.eu/germany/
Video(s)	German LL Short video: https://youtu.be/yKal3eVOIUu Demo Day video: https://youtu.be/TCNMT-wheVo Use Case 1 video: https://youtu.be/wMXOYBbjGDQ

Photos

3.7.3. Italian Living Lab Demo Day in Turin

PoDIUM hosted its second demonstration event on 15 October 2025 in Turin, Italy, showcasing the two Italian Living Lab use cases, which address safety in complex traffic environments, from busy urban intersections to tunnels without satellite coverage. Organised with the support of LINKS Foundation, Autostrada del Brennero, Stellantis-CRF, SWARCO, and TIM, the event demonstrated how PDI solutions can bring CCAM innovations from research into real-world conditions.

The event featured a live demonstration of the urban intersection use case, highlighting how data from roadside sensors, C-ITS infrastructure, traffic lights, and a digital twin can support safer interactions between connected vehicles and VRUs. A video presentation complemented this with the tunnel safety use case deployed on the Brenner highway, where advanced sensing and positioning technologies

enable reliable vehicle tracking and real-time guidance in GPS-denied environments. Further details on the demonstration setup, can be found in Table 11 below.

Table 11: Italian Living Lab Demonstration details

Living Lab	Italian Living Lab
Date	15 October 2025
Demo Site	Corso Spezia, Turin
Agenda	<p>09:00 – 11:00 SCALE-PODIUM Liaison (only PoDIUM partners)</p> <p>11:00 – 11:15 Coffee and Demo Registration</p> <p>11:15 – 11:20 Welcome - Elena Deambrogio Municipality of Turin</p> <p>11:20 – 11:30 Opening (ICCS)</p> <p>11:30 – 11:40 Living Lab intro (LINKS)</p> <p>11:40 – 12:30 UC5 Presentation & video (BRE-CRF-LINKS)</p> <p>12:30 – 13:00 UC4 Presentation (CRF-LINKS-SWM-TIM)</p> <p>13:00 – 14:00 Lunch break</p> <p>14:00 – 14:30 Transfer to Corso Spezia crosspoint</p> <p>14:30 – 17:30 Live Streaming Demo from the car</p>
Use Case(s) in focus and demonstrated scenario(s)	<p>UC4 – Trusted Cooperative Perception for Intersection Manoeuvre Assistance (Urban)</p> <p>The demonstration showed how trusted data from multiple sources, including roadside sensors, C-ITS infrastructure, and traffic lights, are fused through a digital twin to help connected vehicles and Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs) safely navigate busy intersections. The system provides guidance to the vehicles and VRUs (using a dedicated smartphone app) to cross safely, demonstrating improved coordination and safety between all road users.</p> <p>UC5 – Risk Management in a Highway Tunnel (Highway)</p> <p>A video presentation illustrated the second Use Case deployed on the A22 Trento Highway targeting risk management in a GPS-denied environment. The scenario combined sensing with dynamic vehicle data to assess tunnel risk levels and support safe traffic operation using highly accurate vehicle positioning.</p>
Main outcome	Successful validation of advanced PDI-supported cooperative perception in urban intersections and effective risk management and positioning in a complex tunnel environment.
Partners Involved	CRF, LINKS, SWARCO, TIM, and BRE
Participants	31 participants (closed event – mostly internal)
Press Release/articles	https://podium-project.eu/a-recap-of-the-podium-italian-living-lab-demonstration-event/
Italian LL web page	https://podium-project.eu/italy/
Video(s)	<p>Italian LL Short video: https://youtu.be/YIYaNu5_zL4</p> <p>Demo Day & UC4 video: https://youtu.be/YRULxO7xm10</p> <p>Use Case 5 video: https://youtu.be/XqMWfzW6rK0</p>

Photos

3.7.4. Final Event & Spanish Living Lab Demo Days in Barcelona

The project held its Final Event on 19 November 2025 in Barcelona, bringing together project partners, industry representatives, and stakeholders from related EU-funded initiatives to present project results, reflect on lessons learned, and discuss pathways towards real-life CCAM deployment. With around 70 participants, the event marked a key milestone for the project and included a live demonstration of the Barcelona Living Lab use case under real traffic conditions.

The Final Event featured presentations from all three Living Labs, highlighting the project’s achievements in Germany, Italy, and Spain, followed by a panel discussion on the transition from research to CCAM deployment in urban environments. In the afternoon, participants attended a live demonstration on Barcelona’s Gran Via Avenue showcasing emergency vehicle prioritisation (a fire truck) and VRU protection (a cyclist), enabled by cooperative PDI.

On 20 November, the Spanish Living Lab hosted a second live demonstration on the C-32 corridor as part of the Autopistas Future Road Lab. The demonstration illustrated real-time responsive traffic management supported by C-V2X, 5G connectivity, AI-based sensing, and a Digital Twin, including a stopped-vehicle scenario and coordinated traffic management via the Traffic Control Centre. Further details on the Final Event and the two Spanish Living Lab demonstrations are provided in Table 12 below.

Table 12: Final Event and Spanish Living Lab Demo Days

Living Lab	Final Event in Barcelona
Date	19 November 2025
Demo Site	Barcelona City Council & Gran Via Avenue

Agenda

 08:30 **Registration**

 09:00 – 10:00 **Opening Sessions**

- Welcome Speech & Barcelona's Vision in Urban Mobility by Àngel López, Director of Mobility, Barcelona City Council (BCN)
- PoDIUM Project Overview (ICCS)

 10:00 – 11:00 **PoDIUM Use Cases Presentations (Part I)**

- German Living Lab: Cooperative Corridor Management in the City of Ulm – UC1 (UULM & BOSCH)
- Italian Living Lab: Trusted Cooperative Perception for Intersection Manoeuvre Assistance - UC4 (LINKS & SWARCO) & Risk Management in a Highway Tunnel - UC5 (BRE)

 11:00 – 11:30 **Coffee Break**

 11:30 – 12:30 **PoDIUM Use Cases Presentations (Part II)**

- Spanish Living Lab: Real-time responsive PDI for CCAM-enabled Traffic Management - UC3 (AAE) & Physical and Digital Infrastructure (PDI) for a User-Centric, CCAM-enabled Traffic Management in Urban Corridors with High Priority Vehicles and Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs) - UC2 (ETRA)

 12:30 – 13:30 **Panel Discussion: Roads of Tomorrow: From Research to CCAM Deployment within Mobility Ecosystems**

Moderator: Míriam Alvarado - Director of Technology Services and Digital Transformation of Infrastructures and Urban Planning, Barcelona City Council (BCN)

- Ana Martínez Roselló, EU Project Manager – ETRA I+D / Augmented CCAM
- Josep Maria Aymami, Head of Market Expansion – Aimsun / CONDUCTOR Project
- Samuel Rodríguez, Technology Consultant in Future Mobility & Smart Cities// Eurecat Madrid Manager / CARMONY
- Cristina Gil Sánchez, Mobility Engineer - Barcelona City Council (BCN)
- Laura Val Ibort, Innovation Officer, EIT Urban Mobility

 13:30 – 14:30 **Lunch break**

 14:30 – 15:00 **Transfer to Use Case 2 Demonstration Site**

 15:00 – 17:00 **UC2 Live Demonstration at Gran Via**

<p>Use Case(s) in focus and demonstrated scenario(s)</p>	<p>UC2 – Physical and Digital Infrastructure (PDI) for a User-Centric, CCAM-enabled Traffic Management in Urban Corridors with High Priority Vehicles and Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First scenario: Prioritisation for an emergency vehicle (EV) — where the infrastructure gives priority to a Firefighters’ vehicle along the corridor, and a connected vehicle communicates with the infrastructure to perform a safe, cooperative manoeuvre. • Second scenario: Protection of Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs) — where pedestrians and cyclists are detected and protected through real-time V2X communication.
<p>Main outcome</p>	<p>Successful validation of real-time cooperative traffic management in a dense urban environment, demonstrating effective emergency vehicle prioritisation and enhanced protection of vulnerable road users through infrastructure-supported V2X communication under real Barcelona traffic conditions.</p>
<p>Partners Involved</p>	<p>ETRA, IDIADA, MILLA, ISFM, RETE, BCN, IMI</p>
<p>Participants</p>	<p>70 participants</p>
<p>Press Release/articles</p>	<p>https://podium-project.eu/podium-final-event-advancing-connected-cooperative-and-automated-mobility-through-smart-infrastructure/</p>

DAY 1 Photos

<p>Date</p>	<p>20 November 2025</p>
<p>Demo Site</p>	<p>Autopistas Operations and Road safety centre and C-32 highway</p>

<p>Use Case(s) in focus and demonstrated scenario(s)</p>	<p>UC3 – Real-time responsive PDI for CCAM-enabled traffic management in cross-border highway corridors</p> <p>The demonstration was carried out on a 12 km section of the C-32 highway between Viladecans and Castelldefels, part of the Autopistas Future Road Lab. The use case evaluated how a responsive Physical and Digital Infrastructure enables continuous cooperation between vehicles, roadside infrastructure, and the Traffic Management Centre to support real-time traffic management under mixed traffic conditions.</p> <p>The demonstrated scenarios included:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stopped-vehicle and incident detection, where AI-based infrastructure sensors identified hazards on the highway and triggered tailored alerts and manoeuvre recommendations delivered directly to in-vehicle HMIs. • Dynamic traffic management strategies, tested under daily commuting flows as well as unexpected events such as congestion or lane obstructions, with real-time monitoring and decision-making by the Traffic Management Centre. • Cross-border corridor operation, validating uninterrupted data exchange and coordinated traffic strategies across operator domains using 5G and C-V2X connectivity. • Connected and automated vehicle interaction, including an automated shuttle responding to infrastructure messages and manoeuvre recommendations. • Vulnerable Road User (VRU) protection, where infrastructure-based risk detection generated simultaneous warnings to vehicles and VRUs via C-ITS communication.
<p>Main Outcome</p>	<p>Successful demonstration of responsive highway traffic management through infrastructure-supported cooperation, improving incident response, traffic efficiency and VRU protection under real cross-border corridor conditions.</p>
<p>Partners Involved</p>	<p>AAE, RETE, ENIDE, TENAL, IDIADA, i2CAT, UPC, MILLA, ISFM</p>
<p>Participants</p>	<p>31 participants (closed event- internal)</p>
<p>Press Release/articles</p>	<p>https://podium-project.eu/podium-demonstrates-real-time-traffic-management-at-the-spanish-living-lab/</p>
<p>Spanish LL web page</p>	<p>https://podium-project.eu/spain/</p>
<p>Videos</p>	<p>Spanish LL Short Video: https://youtu.be/xDgITNDLA1g Final event and Spanish LL demo video: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5Z3lhBGNdL0 Use Case 2 video: https://youtu.be/IJtLL42DtZA Use Case 3 video: https://youtu.be/FPET2lt2aCU</p>
<p>DAY 2 Photos</p>	

4. Conclusion

This deliverable has presented a comprehensive overview of the dissemination activities carried out by the PoDIUM consortium throughout the project's lifecycle, from October 2022 to December 2025, in line with the strategy defined in Deliverable D7.4. **Deliverable 7.9** illustrates how dissemination was integrated as a continuous and structured effort enhancing the visibility, understanding and dissemination of PoDIUM's goals, activities and outcomes across key stakeholders and the wider CCAM ecosystem.

Overall, PoDIUM successfully and effectively delivered on its dissemination commitments and, in many areas, exceeded the targets initially set. The consortium maintained a strong presence at pertinent scientific, technical and industry events, with **49 presentations** delivered across **42 conferences and events**, including major international gatherings such as ITS European and World Congresses, EUCAD, IEEE conferences and other key CCAM-related occasions. Exhibition activities significantly surpassed expectations, featuring involvements in 11 stands and booths across major ITS and mobility events in Europe and beyond.

Scientific dissemination concentrated mainly on peer-reviewed conference proceedings leading to **22 published papers** and one doctoral thesis deriving from PoDIUM research. Although no journal articles were completed during the project timeframe, multiple research findings have attained submission quality and are either currently under review or scheduled for submission after the project ends, securing ongoing scientific influence beyond the project duration. All public results have been made openly accessible through the project website and the PoDIUM Zenodo community, in line with EU Open Science principles.

The project also prioritised stakeholder engagement and the accessibility of outcomes via webinars, videos, live demonstrations and non-scientific publications. As initially planned, **five webinars** were organised by the project, addressing the platform architecture, Living Lab advancements and the project's conclusive results, with recorded sessions and videos further extending their reach. PoDIUM exceeded its original video production target by delivering **nine videos**, supporting dissemination at events, online platforms and exhibitions. **Three demonstration events** in Germany, Italy and Spain, combined with the **Final Event** in Barcelona, showcased PoDIUM's five use cases in real traffic conditions and provided tangible evidence of the project's technical achievements.

The dissemination strategy, execution and reporting followed a clear internal procedure, ensuring alignment with project dissemination goals, European Commission requirements and brand identity, while enabling efficient tracking, documentation and promotion of activities. Regular monitoring through WP7 meetings and coordination calls supported consistency and quality throughout the project.

In conclusion, PoDIUM's dissemination activities effectively supported the project's overall objectives by raising awareness, fostering dialogue with key stakeholders, strengthening its scientific profile and ensuring broad access to its results. The dissemination outcomes achieved provide a solid foundation for the exploitation, uptake and further development of PoDIUM's results beyond the end of the project, contributing to the wider deployment of Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility solutions in Europe.

Annex – PoDIUM Final Brochure

PODIUM advances the integration of Physical and Digital Infrastructure (PDI) to enable safer, more efficient, and more reliable road automation. By addressing key challenges in connectivity, cooperation, data management, interoperability, and reliability, the project paves the way for the large-scale deployment of Connected, Cooperative, and Automated Mobility (CCAM) solutions across Europe.

Through extensive real-life demonstrations

in three Living Labs – in Germany, Italy, and Spain – PODIUM has tested innovative CCAM use cases in urban, highway, and cross-border environments, showing how advanced infrastructure can support vehicles and road users alike.

The PODIUM Living Labs

Germany: Testing cooperative urban corridor management for improved safety and efficiency in complex city traffic.

Italy: Demonstrating enhanced safety and reliability in complex environments – from urban intersections to GNSS-denied motorway tunnels.

Spain: Showcasing real-time, data-driven traffic management in urban corridors and on highways, supporting priority vehicles, Vulnerable Road Users (VRU) protection and cross-border continuity.

Use Case #2
PDI for Use-Centric, CCAM-enabled Traffic Management in Urban Corridors with High Priority Vehicles and VRUs

Use Case 2 enhances urban traffic management in Barcelona by enabling real-time data exchange between CAVs and the infrastructure. Three scenarios were demonstrated in a complex urban environment: Emergency Vehicle (EV) priority, traffic optimisation, and VRU protection. Together, they address real-time traffic light priority for EVs, traffic analytics and congestion warning based on connected vehicle data, and proactive collision-risk alerts for CAVs and VRUs.

Key results and technological advancements

- The use case successfully achieved its key objectives of validating the physical and digital infrastructure (PDI), edge computing (MEC), and their integration with Barcelona's traffic management and emergency response systems.
- Scenario 1 successfully anticipated the arrival of EVs and activated the green light early before they reached the road segment, achieving dynamic EV priority.
- Scenario 2 enhanced the MISTRAL Smart Mobility Platform by utilising connected vehicle data (position and origin-destination) to generate traffic metrics and facilitate optimal control strategies.
- Scenario 3 demonstrated clear safety benefits: the C-V2X warning enabled earlier braking and reduced deceleration magnitude, thus validating the targets for low latency and softer manoeuvres.
- Warnings for all scenarios (EV approach, congestion and collision risk) are broadcast as standardised C-ITS DENM messages via a hybrid 5G/C-V2X network. These warnings are relayed to the driver via the Human-Machine Interface (HMI), and CAVs can also react autonomously to them.

Challenges and recommendations for deployment

- The main challenge was the difficulty of testing the scenario due to heavy mixed traffic and complex VRU patterns in the Barcelona test site (the Gran Via Corridor).
- Ultimately, the CAV was unable to obtain the necessary permits to conduct tests in Spain. Consequently, the CAV trials had to be relocated to a closed circuit in France. Nevertheless, the full set of planned trials involving connected vehicles were carried out in Barcelona, with no impact on the results.
- Recommendations include prioritising the establishment of streamlined, harmonised European regulatory frameworks for CAV testing.

Use Case #1
Cooperative Corridor Management in the City of Ulm

Use Case 1 validates a cooperative local environment model and planner to manage complex urban traffic situations, such as a blocked lane. The focus is on improving safety and efficiency when vehicles and VRUs (e.g., cyclists) must share a constrained road section. The setup combines onboard and infrastructure sensors with different communication technologies (5G cm- and mm-wave, and 60 GHz WiFi) to ensure high availability and reliability.

Key results and technological advancements

- A local environment model for the intersection was developed using data from connected road users alone, and in combination with infrastructure sensors, including reliability checks.
- A reliable multi-connectivity approach (5G + 60 GHz WiFi) enabled fast and reliable cooperative decision-making.
- VRU protection improved through coordination between Connected Automated Vehicles (CAVs) and connected VRUs.
- Cooperative corridor management led to improvements in traffic efficiency and/or safety.
- PODIUM's architecture enabled offloading complex CAV functions to the MEC.

Challenges and recommendations for deployment

- Traffic steering and load balancing across heterogeneous communication technologies can be efficient in transport-layer schedulers, but intensive packet processing for collision-free duplication/deduplication requires hardware support for high throughputs and should be decoupled from transport-layer scheduling.
- Standardised messages only should be used as the interface between different components to facilitate interaction between the server planner and the local vehicle planners.
- Accurate local environment models can be built with minimal infrastructure, enabling manoeuvre coordination using only communication modules and an edge server.
- Vehicles can be augmented with enhanced or even supplementary functionalities by leveraging function offloading to the MEC. This is much improved by high-bandwidth networks like 5G and multi-connectivity.

Use Case #3
Real-time Responsive PDI for CCAM-enabled Traffic Management in the Mediterranean Cross-Border Corridor

Use Case 3 demonstrates how a responsive PDI system enables real-time cooperation between vehicles, road users, and operators to improve safety and traffic flow under mixed traffic conditions. On the C-32 highway near Barcelona, connected vehicles exchanged data with the infrastructure to receive alerts and manoeuvre recommendations for efficient daily commuting and unexpected safety incidents. The use case also addressed seamless cross-border data continuity and coordination between traffic management centres, an on-demand automated shuttle service, and a VRU Safety application issuing simultaneous alerts to pedestrians and vehicles.

Key results and technological advancements

- An ETSI-compliant V2X communications protocol stack, including C-ITS messages was implemented in vehicles and the edge server.
- Two V2X gateways enabled the transmissions of C-ITS messages over both C-V2X and 5G networks.
- A Digital Twin based on a Local Dynamic Map (LDM) was implemented to store road-user and infrastructure data and to predict nearby vehicle positions during network interruptions.
- The Traffic Management Centre fused connected vehicle and video analytics data from traffic cameras to detect traffic flows and hazards, launching responsive traffic strategies in real time.
- The VRU Safety app transmits pedestrian locations with C-ITS messages and sends collision-risk alerts to vehicles and pedestrians.
- On-board units and the HMI enabled any vehicle to connect with nearby vehicles (V2V communication) and infrastructure, receiving alerts and recommended strategies; automated vehicles can apply them autonomously.

Challenges and recommendations for deployment

- Cross-border 5G roaming limitations disrupted seamless connectivity and limited testing of edge – cloud communication across operator domains. C-V2X antennas were used to bridge coverage gaps and maintain C-ITS message delivery.
- Integrating OBUS, 5G modems, HMIs, and logging equipment required extensive calibration and compatibility checks; modular, standardised interfaces would streamline future deployments.
- Coordinating communication between vehicles, roadside units, and the PODIUM MEC platform demanded significant integration and tuning; layered testing and orchestration monitoring tools are recommended to ensure robustness and interoperability.
- In-vehicle HMI warnings must be intuitive and non-distracting; UX co-design, system fretuning and usability testing improve clarity.
- The private experimental 5G network used in trials had stability issues; future tests should use commercial networks for carrier-grade reliability.
- CAV testing was not possible due to permit limitations; harmonised EU regulations are needed to enable future cross-border CAV demonstrations.

Use Case #4

Trusted Cooperative Perception for Intersection Manoeuvre Assistance

Use Case 4 demonstrates an infrastructure-based application that assists CAVs at urban intersections while protecting VRUs. Deployed in Turin, the system fuses trusted data from multiple sources, including roadside sensors, C-ITS infrastructure, and traffic lights through a digital twin. It then provides guidance to the CAVs and connected VRUs to safely pass a busy urban intersection. The Use Case demonstrates that the digital infrastructure can provide the necessary information to road users to improve safety at intersections.

Overview of results and technological advancements

- An infrastructure-based awareness and assistance system, based on a Digital Twin and a dedicated VRU intersection-movement assist application, providing collective perception data, warnings and recommendations to CAVs approaching an intersection.
- An on-board communication unit (OBU) with trust computing capabilities that allows protection of OBU applications and infrastructure data upstream against integrity attacks on C-ITS stations.
- ETSI-compliant protocol stack (GeoNetworking, BTP, C-ITS) on the OBU for seamless communication.
- Precise positioning strategies for CAV sub-meter localization utilizing mass market hardware.
- On-board applications, on the electronic control unit of the vehicle, performing V2X and sensors data fusion and assisting the driver or the automated driving function with enhanced awareness of VRUs and other road users at urban intersections.
- A gateway ensuring low latency and robust data exchange between the intra-vehicle network and the external system, including C-ITS messages and precise positioning data.
- Seamless interaction with 5G MEC applications via SEN platform services, ensuring adequate response times for real-time decision-making.

Challenges and recommendations for deployment

- The performance assessment – particularly the actual advantage over human driving decisions – should be conducted in more controlled environments due to the complexity of real-world manoeuvres.
- Despite several technical and organisational issues that affected integration timelines, the use case reached its final operational state in time for the Turin demonstration.
- A living lab on public roads is very useful for evaluating collective perception, but it needs to be complemented by test-track experiments where VRU trajectories and CAV behaviour can be safely measured.

Use Case #5

Risk Management in a Highway Tunnel

Use Case 5 addresses safety and cooperative-awareness challenges in tunnels, where satellite positioning is not available. In a tunnel on the Brenner Motorway, the service monitors traffic, assesses real-time risks and sends warnings to incoming CAVs. Roadside sensors count and classify vehicles in the tunnel, while a Digital Twin processes this data and sends warnings to CAVs in case drivers need to change lane or reduce their speed. Inside the tunnel, indoor positioning is maintained either through a synthetic GNSS signal delivered by dedicated infrastructure or through trilateration using vehicle and roadside units, ensuring cooperative services continue even without open sky.

Overview of results and technological advancements

- A real-time risk assessment system integrating multi-source data to generate a digital twin of the tunnel environment.
- Context-aware warnings and risk-mitigating actions based on validated sensor and vehicle data, improving the quality of the outgoing C-ITS messages.
- Secure and trustworthy communication protocols using Trusted Platform Module (TPM) technology.
- Dynamic risk management strategies that can trigger automated responses in CAVs for lane changes or speed adjustments.
- An on-board positioning system using dead-reckoning based on maps and lane detection as well as V2I trilateration techniques for lane-level localization of the vehicle inside the tunnel, and GNSS with Real Time kinematics in open sky conditions.
- Development of a vehicle-based collective perception complying with ETSI standard and data fusion system to obtain extended perception even inside the tunnel.
- Integration of positioning system, V2I hazard warning and V2V collective perception and data fusion into CAV prototype for Cooperative Adaptive Cruise Control (C-ACC) and SAE L4 Operational Design Domain in tunnel scenarios.

Challenges and recommendations for deployment

- Positioning systems based on V2I trilateration are highly dependent on the relative position of the roadside units. Along the highway, especially in tunnels there is little margin to install them.
- The multi-source positioning system was calibrated and optimised for transitions between open sky and tunnel.
- Extensive tests along the A22 showed good performance in these transitions, though moderate GNSS degradation still occurred in environments characterized by narrow valleys. These cases and the so-called "urban canyon" conditions should be addressed when calibrating a production-ready system.
- Experiments on the data fusion of Cooperative Perception Messages (CPM) and sensors performed well under Living Lab operational conditions (10 CPM per second). Through simulations, possible degradation effects were evident when exchanging CPM less frequently (threshold of acceptable error found at around 3 CPM per second). Further studies should be performed, with different kind of data fusion systems involved, to consolidate the value of minimum frequency of CPM fulfilling the cooperative use cases.

"PoDIUM has strengthened the foundations for CCAM deployment by advancing physical and digital infrastructure technologies and validating connectivity and cooperation enablers in real traffic environments. Project results show measurable improvements in safety—especially vulnerable road user protection, vehicle-to-infrastructure (V2I) communication and traffic efficiency supporting higher levels of automation across Europe."

Dr. Angelos Anaditis
PoDIUM Project Coordinator
Research & Development Director, ICCS

Consortium

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